

RI4C2 – Research and Innovation for Cities and Citizens

Survey on R&I Needs of EC2U Alliance

General Results

DELIVERABLE 2.1
MONTH 12

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Introduction

Survey on R&I Needs of EC2U Alliance is part of the project 'Research & Innovation for Cities & Citizens (RI4C2)', a joint project of the member universities of the EC2U Alliance (universities of Coimbra, Alexandru Ioan Cuza of Iași, Friedrich Schiller Jena, Pavia, Poitiers, Salamanca and Turku). The overall objective of the RI4C2 project is to strengthen collaboration and knowledge circulation in research and innovation within the EC2U Alliance and, finally, to create a shared Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem. The RI4C2 project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement 101035803.

The survey targets the seven EC2U university communities, the seven city and regional administrations, all EC2U associated partners and a selection of other economic and social stakeholders. The survey has two main aims:

1. To identifying priority interdisciplinary R&I activities that should be carried out inside the three existing EC2U Virtual Institutes (VI for Health and Well-Being, VI for Quality Education - Language and Cultural Diversity, VI for Sustainable Cities and Communities).
2. To identify the main research topics of the new EC2U virtual institutes that will be created next year.

Participation in this survey was entirely voluntary and anonymous. The target could decline to participate or withdraw from the survey without providing an explanation at any time.

The anonymous data collected in this study will be used (1) to identify priority interdisciplinary R&I activities that should be carried out inside the three existing EC2U Virtual Institutes, (2) to identify the main research topics of the new EC2U virtual institutes that will be created next year and (3) to identify attitudes and perceptions on research policy making.

Participation in the survey took around 10–15 minutes to every respondent. The survey was open from 1 June 2022 until 15 July 2022.

1. Methodology and technical sheet

In this study, the target population/ universe was the university community and social agents linked to the following universities of the EC2U alliance:

- University of Coimbra (Portugal)
- University of Iasi (Romania)
- University of Jena (Germany)
- University of Pavia (Italy)
- University of Poitiers (France)
- University of Salamanca (Spain)
- University of Turku (Finland)

The sampling design or sampling technique refers to how the sample is selected from the population mentioned above. In the present study, a non-probability sampling technique was chosen, characterised by the following elements.

-Convenience sampling, as specific segments of the population have been selected for the collection of information.

-Snowball sampling, characterised by the possibility of access to the survey through third party mailings. In addition, exponential sampling has been chosen: each individual can invite two or more individuals to participate. Thus, the more people participate in the study, the more people are added to the study.

As the choice of elements is not random, but at the discretion of the research team itself, it is not possible to estimate the sampling error. To avoid the risk of community bias in which a subgroup of individuals within each target is accessed and recruitment of new members does not leave that subgroup, the research team has made a specific initial selection of individuals that ensures that any existing subgroup is accessible in the network of contacts of the initial individuals.

This technique is the only one possible when targeting small groups where it is not possible to have a sample frame.

The data collection technique was carried out using the CAWI (Computer Assisted Web Interviewing) system, by means of e-mails and distribution of links with access to the data collection platform. The online platform used is LIMESURVEY, developers of the open source survey software, facilitating data security and transparency in data collection.

All surveys have followed a strict data protection protocol with an acceptance by the respondent of the following terms:

Data Controllers:

University of Salamanca, University of Pavia

Contact persons in matters concerning the project: Raúl Sánchez Prieto (ec2u2@usal.es), Luigi Santangelo (luigi.santangelo@unipv.it).

Contact information of the Data Protection Officer: secr.general@usal.es (https://www.usal.es/proteccion_datos).

Persons processing personal data in the study: Only the members of the project team participate in the processing of personal data. Personal data will not be shared outside the project team.

Duration of the processing of personal data: 1.6.2022 - 31.8.2024. No direct personal identifiers will be collected. The data not containing direct identifiers will be stored for 5 years after the completion of the project and will be

Personal data is processed following a legitimate interest pursued by the controller or by a third party

The processing of personal data is based on the mission of the University. The information will also be used to support the partner universities of the EC2U Alliance in designing a common research and innovation agenda.

We collect the field of science and the position from all participants. No other information will be collected.

The data is collected using LimeSurvey data collection tool located at the EC2U Connect Centre. Lime Survey is a secure web application. The data collected will be stored and backed up in the secured cloud service of the EC2U Connect Centre provided by the University of Pavia. By adhering to this procedure, we are able to guarantee that the data will be kept safely on the University's own servers. The folders of the Connect Centre are accessed by a personal, password-protected organisational account, and only the members of the project team are given access rights to the folder.

Personal data will not be transferred to third parties or to countries outside the EU or the European Economic Area.

Registered data will not be used for automatic decision making or profiling.

The research material collected will be archived without identifiers

As a data subject, you have the following rights: rights to obtain information on the processing of personal data, the right of access, the right to rectification, the right to erasure, the right to restriction of processing and the right to object.

For more information on your rights as a data subject, you may contact Raúl Sánchez Prieto (ec2u2@usal.es). You also have the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority if you think your personal data has been processed in violation of applicable data protection laws. Contact information of the Data Protection Ombudsman: Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (Electronic Office: <https://sedeagpd.gob.es/sede-electronica-web/>).

2. Executive summary

The survey conducted at the 7 universities between 1 June and 15 July 2022 had a total of 1855 responses. The best participation was obtained by doctoral students and professors and researchers with 544 and 515 completed questionnaires respectively. The lowest participation was obtained in the case of social partners and stakeholders, with only 95 completed questionnaires.

In any case, this is a statistically relevant sample for an estimated population of 160,000 students and 20,000 administrative staff, lecturers and researchers.

The universities with the highest participation were the University of Coimbra and the University of Salamanca. The universities of Iasi, Poitiers have participated acceptably, with significantly lower participation in the case of the universities of Pavia, Jena and Turku. Low response rate of some EC2U partners could be partly explained by the formal closing during summer.

For specific details of the preferences expressed by each group surveyed in the evaluation questions ("Likert scale analysis"), we recommend that you refer to the detailed report. In this executive summary we will limit to synthesising the responses expressed in terms of preferred research fields and specialisations in the five surveys.

Survey 1

In survey 1, distributed among **university managers**, conclusive results were obtained regarding the research topics that should be a priority for society: **medical sciences** (13%), the field with the greatest consensus, technology (9.1%) and biological sciences (8.2%); in this same item but in relation to the preferred research specialities for their university, again, medical sciences (11.8%), appear in first place, followed by humanities, art and literature (9.45%) and technology (8.5%).

In terms of specific fields of research, university leaders prefer "**cultural studies**" (14.7%) and teaching (10.8%), followed by linguistics and modern languages (9.0%) for their respective universities in the social sciences and humanities. In the field of science and health, the preferred fields are: **environmental technology** (14.7%), climatology (13.9%), circular economy (11.6%) and oceanography (13.9%).

Survey 2

Survey 2 was distributed to socio-economic actors and stakeholders relevant to each university in their respective cities and regions of influence. Although the number of responses obtained is not high, the results obtained are as follows: **logic** (13.8%), law and legal sciences (13.8%) and medical sciences (10.9%) are the fields that receive the greatest preference as research topics that should be a priority for society as a whole.

When asked the same question about the reference university in their city, socio-economic agents prefer: **anthropology** (16.7%), ahead of medical sciences (12.3%) or technology (9.5%).

In the social sciences and humanities, five areas are above 10%: **teaching** (15.5%), educational planning (15%), educational theory (12.4%), linguistics and classical languages (11.9%) and cultural studies (10.9%).

Socio-economic actors advocate "**environmental technology**" (18.1%), 13.3% prefer "agronomy" and 11.4% oceanography as priority research fields in the field of science and health.

Survey 3

Survey 3, addressed to **professors and research staff**, was the second most frequently answered survey across all 7 universities. Their preferred research topics for the near future are: **medical sciences** (16.7%), technology (11.8%) and life sciences (7.9%).

As preferred research topics at their university, professors and researchers choose medical sciences (15.2%), technology (10.8%), life sciences (8.5%) and humanities (7.1%).

In the social sciences and humanities, the preferred research specialisations are: **linguistics and modern languages** (11.0%), teaching (10.2%), educational planning (10.5%) and cultural studies (10.5%).

The priority research fields for teachers and researchers in science and health are **environmental technology** (14.9%), climatology (14.1%) and agronomy (10.9%).

Survey 4

Of the 5 sectors of the university community, **PhD students** are the most involved in research at the 7 universities. For them, the most important topics for future research are **medical sciences**

(14.5%), technology (11.5%) and pedagogy (6.7%). When the question is limited to the field of their university, the same preference is expressed: medical sciences (12.1%), technology (10.7%) and pedagogy (6.1%).

PhD students prefer the following research fields that should be a priority at their university in the social sciences and humanities: **educational theory and cultural studies** (13.7%), followed by teacher education (12.3%) and educational planning (12.3%).

Among the main preferred research fields in science and health, **environmental technology** (15.1%), climatology (14.3%) and agronomy (10.5%) are mentioned.

Survey 5

Survey 5 was sent to students, **administrative staff and stakeholders** in each university community. The priority research topics for these 3 social groups are: **medical sciences** (14.8%) technology (11.3%) and psychology with 7.1%. Identical results when the question is restricted to the area of the university to which they belong: medical sciences (14.1%), technology (10.2%) and psychology (6.7%).

In the area of social sciences and humanities, the subjects preferred by respondents are: **linguistics and modern languages** (13.4%), pedagogy (10.3%), educational planning (11.1%) and cultural studies (10.8%).

As for the research fields that should be prioritised at their university, the responses mainly point to **climatology** (13.6%), environmental technology (13.4%) and economics of climate change (10.2%).

3. Analysis Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)

1. Technical sheet

Table 1 shows the valid questionnaires for each part of the questionnaire. From part A, 212 questionnaires were collected, from A+B, 166 questionnaires, from A+B+C, 159 questionnaires, as in part A+B+C+D and the last one, 31 questionnaires (A+B+C+D+E).

Table 1 : Valid responses

Platform accesses	327
Questionnaires started	212
Completed questionnaires	
Part A	212
Part A + B	166
Part A +B + C	159
Part A + B + C + D	159
Part A + B + C + D + E	31

2. Part A

52% of the responses came from the University of Coimbra, followed by the University of Salamanca (20.8%) and, at a greater distance, the University of Poitiers.

Figure 1 : University

The following graph (Graph 2) shows the position of the persons interviewed. Fifty-four percent are in the "other" category, 20.3% are Research Group/Institute Directors and 7.1% are

Department Directors. To a lesser extent, Dean of Faculty (5.2%), Vice-Rector (4.2%) and Rector (0.9%) also appear

Figure 2 : Position

3. Part B

Section B of the questionnaire relates the scientific activity of the university community and its position in society. In fact, as we can see in this first graph (Graph 3), 32.5% of the university managers surveyed somewhat agree that "public opinion should play an important role in guiding decisions on scientific issues", compared with 20.5% who neither agree nor disagree and 30% who disagree.

Similar to the previous question, 34.3% agreed with the following statement: "political actors (local and regional government bodies, political parties) should play an important role in guiding political decisions on scientific issues"; 30.7% disagreed.

Figure 3 : Degree of agreement with: Public opinion has an important role to play in guiding decisions on scientific issues

Figure 4 : Degree of agreement with: Socio-economic actors have an important role to play in guiding policy decisions on scientific issues.

Figure 5 : Degree of agreement with: Political actors (local and regional government bodies, political parties) have an important role to play in guiding political decisions on scientific issues.

Figure 6 : Degree of agreement with: Students should play an important role in identifying research topics relevant to society.

Regard to this statement, there is a higher aggregate consensus (Figure 4), with 39.2% agreeing somewhat that "socio-economic actors should play an important role in guiding policy decisions on scientific issues". The degree of agreement is lower when assessing the fact that "political actors (local and regional government bodies, political parties) should play an important role in guiding policy decisions on scientific issues", with 12.7% strongly agreeing and 34.3% somewhat agreeing, based on the results in Figure 5.

Similarly, 39.2% also somewhat agree with the following statement, "students should play an important role in identifying research topics relevant to society".

Table 2 : Assessment of priority research topics for society in the near future (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage		Frequency	Percentage
Logic	6	0,8%	Physics	24	3,3%
Medical Sciences	95	13,0%	Demography	23	3,2%
Linguistics	14	1,9%	Psychology	32	4,4%
Mathematics	29	4,0%	Chemistry	13	1,8%
Technology	66	9,1%	Economic Sciences	22	3,0%
Pedagogy	37	5,1%	Humanities, Arts and Literature	41	5,6%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	7	1,0%	Biological Sciences	60	8,2%
Anthropology	10	1,4%	Geography	13	1,8%
Political Science	20	2,7%	Sociology	30	4,1%
			Space Sciences	27	3,7%
			History	41	5,6%
			Ethics	36	4,9%

Agricultural sciences	38	5,2%
Law and legal sciences	19	2,6%
Philosophy	26	3,6%
Total	729	100,0%

Table 3 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	10	1,4%
Medical Sciences	82	11,8%
Linguistics	25	3,6%
Mathematics	27	3,9%
Technology	59	8,5%
Pedagogy	35	5,0%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	8	1,2%
Anthropology	11	1,6%
Political Science	16	2,3%

Physics	25	3,6%
Demography	12	1,7%
Psychology	27	3,9%
Chemistry	22	3,2%
Economic Sciences	26	3,7%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	65	9,4%
Biological Sciences	35	5,0%
Geography	13	1,9%
Sociology	25	3,6%
Space Sciences	26	3,7%
History	36	5,2%
Ethics	32	4,6%
Agricultural sciences	28	4,0%
Law and legal sciences	25	3,6%
Philosophy	25	3,6%
Total	695	100,0%

There is more conclusive data in the previous multiple-choice tables. In the first of the tables (Table 2), three priority research topics stand out, according to the university community, medical sciences (13%), the area with the greatest consensus, technology (9.1%) and biological sciences (8.2%); in the second of the responses, on this same item (Table 3), again, medical sciences (11.8%), appear in first place, followed by humanities, art and literature (9.45) and technology (8.5%).

There is, on the other hand, a high degree of consensus (70%) regarding the notion that "research in Culture, Education and Languages has a mostly positive effect on society".

Figure 7 : Degree of agreement with: Research in Culture, Education and Languages has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 8 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

More specifically, Graph 8 evaluates the different priority research fields at their university of origin. 14.7% identified "cultural studies" and 10.8% "teaching", while none of the other responses exceeded 10%.

University managers, logically enough, show a majority consensus (64.2%) on the following statement: "research in sustainability has a mostly positive effect on society", as can be seen in Graph 9.

Figure 9 : Degree of agreement with: Sustainability research has a mostly positive effect on society

If in the previous case, "cultural studies" and teaching were the priority research fields, in this second response (Graph 10), four fields of interest emerge: environmental technology (14.7%), climatology (13.9%), circular economy (11.6%) and oceanography (10.7%).

Figure 10 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

81.3% of those interviewed agreed (strongly agree), as shown in Graph 11, with the statement: "health research has a mostly positive effect on society".

Preventive medicine (11%) and public health (10.1%) are the two priority research topics, according to the responses obtained (Table 4), by the managers of the university community in the field of health and welfare.

Figure 11 : Degree of agreement with: Health research has a mostly positive impact on society

Table 4 : Assessment of research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being research (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Psychology	59	7,9%
Pharmacodynamics	12	1,6%
Human physiology	26	3,5%
Clinical sciences	44	5,9%

Pharmacology	35	4,7%
Immunology	53	7,1%
Epidemiology	56	7,5%
Preventive medicine	81	10,9%
Microbiology	15	2,0%
Forensic sciences	4	0,5%
Psychiatry	39	5,2%
Molecular biology	29	3,9%
Occupational medicine	13	1,7%
Public health	75	10,1%
Virology	25	3,4%
Internal medicine	10	1,3%
Surgery	14	1,9%
Neurosciences	72	9,7%
Nutritional sciences	33	4,4%
Toxicology	10	1,3%
Pathology	8	1,1%
Human biology	32	4,3%
Total	745	100,0%

The following graphs show different responses to certain questions related to climate, sustainable development and food security. 83% agree (63.5% strongly agree) with the statement "research on Human Rights and Sustainable Development has a mostly positive effect on society"; the majority of managers (64.5% strongly agree) reflect their consensus when asked whether "research on climate-related issues has a mostly positive effect on society" and, to a lesser extent, 57.2% (strongly agree), "research on decent work, economic growth and circular economy has a mostly positive effect on society".

In Figure 15, 63.3% of respondents "strongly agree" that "research on poverty reduction and food security has a positive effect on society".

The heading "research on affordable and clean energy has a mostly positive effect on society" has a consensus of (71.1%). Finally, 56.6% strongly agree with: "Research on a global agreement on Sustainable Development has a mostly positive effect on society".

Figure 12 : Degree of agreement with: Human Rights and Sustainable Development research has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 13 : Degree of agreement with: Research on climate-related issues has a mostly positive effect on society

Figure 14 : Degree of agreement with: Research on decent work, economic growth and circular economy has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 15 : Degree of agreement with: Research on poverty reduction and food security has a positive effect on society.

Figure 16 : Degree of agreement with: Affordable and clean energy research has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 17 : Degree of agreement with: Research on a global agreement on sustainable development has a mostly positive

4. Part C

Consensus is lower when assessing whether "scientists and policy makers lack regular and well-supported opportunities to meet and exchange ideas", with 36.5% "strongly agreeing" and 37.7% "somewhat agreeing", as shown in Figure 18. The next statement, "researchers take appropriate initiatives to increase acceptance of research by policy makers", reflects less consensus, with 11.3% "strongly agreeing" and 30.2% "somewhat agreeing".

On the other hand, as we can see in graph 20, there is greater agreement (50.3%, strongly agree), as well as 26.4%, somewhat agree, when it is pointed out that "insufficient funding of research structures and activities is the main obstacle to university policy". In turn, 30.8% (strongly agree) and 26.4% (somewhat agree) also support the point that "researchers can expect recognition, reward and support for their work from employers, funders and peers".

Figure 18 : Degree of agreement with: Scientists and policy makers lack regular and well-supported opportunities to meet and exchange ideas.

Figure 19 : Degree of agreement with: Researchers take appropriate initiatives to increase the acceptance of research by policy makers.

Figure 20 : Degree of agreement with: Insufficient funding of research structures and activities is the main obstacle to university policy.

Figure 21 :Degree of agreement with: Researchers can expect recognition, reward and support for their work from employers, funders and peers.

In this respect, 47.2% of respondents strongly agree, as do 35.2% (somewhat agree) when it is stated that "policy makers and academics often have different priorities". In the next graph (Figure 23), there is somewhat less agreement (33.3%, strongly agree) with the statement that "socio-economic actors (e.g. local and regional businesses) and university policy makers often have different priorities".

More than half of the sample (51.6% strongly agree), to which could be added 37.7%, who say they "somewhat agree", when assessing whether "policy makers and researchers often have different priorities", compared to a lower consensus (32.1% strongly agree), although 44% say they somewhat agree with the statement, "researchers and socio-economic actors often have different priorities" (Figure 25).

Figure 22 : Degree of agreement with: Policy makers and academics tend to have different priorities

policy makers often have different priorities.

Figure 23 : Degree of agreement with: Socio-economic actors (e.g. local and regional businesses) and university

Figure 24 : Degree of agreement with: Policy-makers and researchers tend to have different priorities

Figure 26 : Degree of agreement with: Political and socio-economic decision-makers tend to have different priorities

Figure 25 : Degree of agreement with: Researchers and socio-economic actors tend to have different priorities

Figure 27 : Degree of agreement with: Researchers do research and science on topics relevant to society as a whole.

There is also a greater consensus among university managers (42.8% strongly agree and 35.8% somewhat agree) that "researchers do research and science on issues relevant to society as a whole" (Figure 27).

5. Part D

International cooperation in research is an action that generates a significant degree of agreement among university managers, with 58.5% strongly agreeing and 30.2% somewhat agreeing with the statement, "we need more international cooperation, for example by

participating in international research teams, to obtain better funding for our research". Similarly, "being part of and actively participating in European research institutes will help us to boost our research" generates a significant level of agreement: 56.6% strongly agree and 30.8% agree, as can be seen in graph 29.

Even greater agreement is reflected in the fact that "funds obtained in different national and international competitions are essential to advance research", for 64% of those interviewed (strongly agree) and, to a lesser extent, 26.4%, somewhat agree (Graph 30). Finally, 56.6% agreed that "sharing research facilities and infrastructures between European universities is essential for high-quality research".

Figure 28 : Degree of agreement with: We need more international cooperation, e.g. by participating in international research teams, to get better funding for our research.

Figure 29 : Degree of agreement with: Being part of and actively participating in European research institutes will help us to boost our research.

Figure 30 : Degree of agreement with: Funds obtained in different national and international competitions are essential to advance research.

Figure 31 : Degree of agreement with: Sharing research facilities and infrastructure among European universities is essential for high-quality research.

6. Part E

In the following, the knowledge fields mentioned in the questionnaire are identified in the open-ended part of the questionnaire. For more detailed field involvement see table 5 with the literal specifications of the survey participants.

- Hunger eradication
- Circular economy
- Anthropology of care
- Sports Science
- Renewable energy
- Sustainable agriculture and livestock farming
- Bridge Natural Sciences and Human and Social Sciences.
- Engineering and Technology
- Humanities and Arts
- Legal and Social Sciences.
- Ethics of scientific research and the social impact of scientific communication.
- Management of services (tourism and leisure)
- Culture and heritage studies
- Territorial cohesion
- Educational sciences
- Sociology
- Psychology
- Neuroscience

Table 5 : Input on relevant research fields in which the EC2U Alliance could start to develop joint projects and Virtual Institutes

- ERRADICAÇÃO DA FOME; - ECONOMIA CIRCULAR; - ANTROPOLOGIA DO CUIDADO.

A Aliança de Universidades Europeias EC2U deve incrementar projetos par aprofessroes / investgadores num conceito semelhante a ERASMUS, mas que obriguem à apresentação eficaz e eficiente de relatórios de participação. Por outro lado a comunidade académica, deve de permitir um acesso mais transparente quer à carreira docente, quer à de investigador.

Apesar da área das Ciências do desporto poder ser incluída na área das ciências de saúde ou das ciências sociais, está tem um grande relevo e capacidade multidisciplinar de relevo para a sociedade, devendo ser considerada como uma área específica em que se podem desenvolver vários trabalhos: 1- Recurso a meios de mobilidade suave - questões pedagógicas, sociais e ambientais. 2 - Investimento público - estatal e municipal - na área do desporto e atividade física; 3 - Impacto na saúde e na economia de um programa de exercício físico em populações de risco de saúde (e.g. diabetes, obesidade, hipertensos) 4 - Desporto como meio de desenvolvimento pessoal, social e ético do indivíduo. Em todos estes exemplos, a perspetiva transnacional permitiria obter boas práticas de outros locais, além de um maior conhecimento do contexto de cada país.

Aunque pertenezco a Humanidades, creo que la financiación debería ir para los temas candentes de nuestra sociedad: economía circular, clima, energías renovables, agricultura y ganadería sostenibles, etc. Todo aquello que implique mejorar la economía de España. Me parece estúpido la importancia que se está dando a las lenguas co-oficiales, fuera de sus respectivas autonomías. Vivimos en un mundo global y deben enfatizarse las lenguas francas internacionales: el inglés y el español. Sí, el español, que hablan 450 millones de personas. No veo la necesidad de aprender gallego, catalán, vasco en Castilla y León.

Bridge Natural Sciences and Human and Social Sciences.

Como arabista y especialista en temas de identidad cultural y religiosa en el occidente islámico creo que deberíamos crear grupos de investigación internacionales, me refiero a un grupo que integre la mayor parte de las universidades participantes en el proyecto europeo EC2U. Creo que será uno de los medios más eficaces para dar visibilidad a un tema que concierne a todos los países europeos, entre otras razones, por la gran importancia que hoy en día representa la población musulmana europea, así como su influencia en las sociedades europeas actuales.

Cualquiera sobre ingeniería y tecnología vendría muy bien para todos.

Em relação a algumas questões e às minhas respostas, julgo que depende muito da área do co conhecimento em causa, por isso, respondi apenas concordo. Penso que em Humanidades e Artes o investimento económico internacional é muito importante, mas não tão necessário ao desenvolvimento da investigação como noutras áreas.

Es esencial que la investigación en los institutos virtuales abarquen varios campos de conocimiento. Las Humanidades, las ciencias, Ciencias médicas, jurídicas y sociales son muy relevantes para la investigación moderna.

Es importante subrayar la importancia en la investigación de las nuevas tecnologías desde los diversos campos del saber etica della ricerca scientifica e misure di impatto sociale della ricerca comunicazione della scienza e cittadinanza scientifica

I believe that there are clear possibilities to bring together the EC2U network's efforts around the following themes, which can be worked on in integrative ways: - service management (tourism and leisure) - culture and heritage studies - territorial cohesion

I did not find in your research direction Ecosystem services and biodiversity. Most of our life, activity and development is based on nature examples, so this direction can contribute substantial to developing new medicine treatments, new technology, new food production solutions and so on.

Il est difficile de se limiter à 5 domaines de recherche prioritaires. Il est important que tous les domaines de la recherche soit soutenus à niveau égal. C'est la multidisciplinarité de la recherche qui permet à la société d'en profiter.

L'Alliance pourrait développer des instituts virtuels correspondant au ODDs n°16, n°10 et n°7.

Les moyens étant restreints, c'est la politique scientifique de l'université et la détermination des priorités locales qui sont déterminant pour l'avancée de la recherche. Les coopérations internationales ne sont utiles que sur des bases locales très solides, ce qui n'est pas toujours le cas.

Ña pergunta que he respondido con un 3 no me quedaba clara.

Para maior aposta na investigação, os/as docentes deveriam ter menos carga letiva, sendo necessário contratar mais recursos humanos para as instituições do ensino superior.

Pedagogy should be replaced by sciences of education because pedagogy is not a disciplinary area per se, but education is. The english on this survey is terrible. Please include feminist and intersectionality studies in the list of appropriate areas of research under "culture, languages, etc".

Sem comentários

Sería de suma importancia abarcar problemas donde la globalización ha generado un gran impacto, como el caso de la desinformación, debido a que la solución depende de la voluntad activa de varios factores en todos los Países que se ven afectados.

Sociologie, Psihologie, Neurostiinte

Studies and scientific works linked to studies on the construction of knowledge by men in all their humanity, plural and ethnically diverse, must be strengthened in the articulated set-field of neuroscience and education, aiming at the necessary modifications to the changes present in contemporary times.

The more multidisciplinary the research with a consortium the better and the more productive.

THIS IS A SIGNIFICANT ACTION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCES.

Un questionnaire est toujours délicat à rédiger. Le sens de celui-ci est difficile à percevoir.

4. Analysis Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)

1. Technical sheet

As shown in table 6, the completed questionnaires from Part A are 66, some less from Part A+B (52 questionnaires), 48 questionnaires (Part A+B+C) and 5 questionnaires (A+B+C+E), in total 171 questionnaires among political and socio-economic actors.

Table 6 : Valid questionnaires

Platform accesses	95
Questionnaires started	66
Completed questionnaires	
Part A	66
Part A + B	52
Part A + B + C	48
Part A + B + C + E	5

2. Part A

Graph 32 shows the responses obtained from each of the universities participating in the project. 48.5% of these responses belong to the University of Salamanca, 24.2% to the University of Poitiers and 9.1% to the University of Coimbra, as the most outstanding universities.

Figure 32 : University of Origin

Regarding the position of the respondents to the survey, 53% belong to a regional administration, 19.7% to a local administration or 12% to a representative of an entrepreneurship association, among the most representative positions.

Figure 33 : Position within the university community

3. Part B

The following four graphs show responses to different questions related to science and its production. At first, 34.6% somewhat agree, and 26.9% strongly agree, with the idea that "public opinion should play an important role in guiding decisions on scientific issues"; to a greater extent, 46.2% somewhat agree with the involvement of socio-economic actors in scientific issues, based on the following statement "Socio-economic actors should play an important role in guiding policy decisions on scientific issues".

The same level of consensus (46.2% somewhat agree) is reflected by the socio-economic actors when assessing the statement that "Political actors (local and regional government bodies, political parties) should play an important role in guiding political decisions on scientific issues".

And finally, according to the data in graph 37, 53.8% agree to a certain degree (somewhat agree) with the statement "Students should play an important role in identifying research topics relevant to society".

Figure 34 : Degree of agreement with: Public opinion has an important role to play in guiding decisions on scientific issues

Figure 36 : Degree of agreement with: Political actors (local and regional government bodies, political parties) have an important role to play in guiding political decisions on scientific issues.

Figure 35 : Degree of agreement with: Socio-economic actors have an important role to play in guiding policy decisions on scientific issues.

Figure 37 : Degree of agreement with: Students should play an important role in identifying research topics relevant to society.

The following table (Table 7) shows the responses to the priority research topics for the future in our societies; above 10% of responses, we find three topics: logic (13.8%), law and legal sciences (13.8%) and medical sciences (10.9%).

Table 7 : Assessment of priority research topics for society in the near future (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	42	13,8%
Medical Sciences	33	10,9%
Linguistics	9	3,0%
Mathematics	11	3,6%
Technology	30	9,9%
Pedagogy	8	2,6%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	3	1,0%
Anthropology	0	0,0%
Political Science	4	1,3%
Physics	8	2,6%
Demography	14	4,6%

Psychology	11	3,6%
Chemistry	6	2,0%
Economic Sciences	13	4,3%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	4	1,3%
Biological Sciences	15	4,9%
Geography	1	0,3%
Sociology	6	2,0%
Space Sciences	9	3,0%
History	3	1,0%
Ethics	8	2,6%
Agricultural sciences	22	7,2%
Law and legal sciences	42	13,8%
Philosophy	2	0,7%
Total	304	100,0%

In regard to the assessment of the priority research fields at the university, the responses obtained (Table 8) indicate, significantly, the following results: anthropology is the field most frequently mentioned (16.7%), ahead of medical sciences (12.3%) or technology (9.5%).

Table 8 : Assessment of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	3	1,2%
Medical Sciences	31	12,3%
Linguistics	7	2,8%
Mathematics	13	5,2%
Technology	24	9,5%
Pedagogy	9	3,6%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	1	0,4%
Anthropology	42	16,7%
Political Science	5	2,0%
Physics	10	4,0%
Demography	11	4,4%
Psychology	11	4,4%
Chemistry	5	2,0%
Economic Sciences	11	4,4%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	9	3,6%
Biological Sciences	13	5,2%
Geography	3	1,2%
Sociology	3	1,2%
Space Sciences	9	3,6%
History	4	1,6%
Ethics	5	2,0%

Agricultural sciences	20	7,9%
Law and legal sciences	2	0,8%
Philosophy	1	0,4%
Total	252	100,0%

Figure 38 : Degree of agreement with: Research in Culture, Education and Languages has a mostly positive effect on society.

More than half of the sample (55.8%) shows a high level of consensus (strongly agree) when it comes to assessing the role of "research in Culture, Education and Languages has a mostly positive effect on society".

With regard to the assessment of the priority research fields at the university, as shown in Graph 39, five fields are rated above 10%: teaching (15.5%), educational planning (15%), educational theory (12.4%), linguistics and classical languages (11.9%) and cultural studies (10.9%).

Figure 39 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

In turn, a large proportion of the sample (71.2%) strongly agreed, plus 26.9% agreed, that "sustainability research has a mostly positive effect on society".

Figure 40 : Degree of agreement with: Sustainability research has a mostly positive effect on society

As for the priority research fields at the university (Figure 41), 18.1% favour "environmental technology", 13.3% "agronomy" and 11.4% "oceanography".

Figure 41 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

In the following graph (Figure 42), a broad consensus of responses (80.8%) strongly agree that "health research has a mostly positive effect on society".

Figure 42 : Degree of agreement with: Health research has a largely positive effect on society

Table 9 shows the results of a multiple-choice question on the assessment of priority research topics in the field of health and well-being. Public health (14%) and preventive medicine (13.1%) are the topics most frequently mentioned by the sample.

Table 9 : Assessment of research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being research (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Psychology	17	7,9%
Pharmacodynamics	5	2,3%
Human physiology	4	1,9%
Clinical sciences	7	3,3%
Pharmacology	13	6,1%
Immunology	20	9,3%
Epidemiology	20	9,3%
Preventive medicine	28	13,1%
Microbiology	5	2,3%
Forensic sciences	0	0,0%
Psychiatry	8	3,7%
Molecular biology	9	4,2%
Occupational medicine	4	1,9%
Public health	30	14,0%
Virology	9	4,2%
Internal medicine	3	1,4%
Surgery	3	1,4%
Neurosciences	12	5,6%
Nutritional sciences	14	6,5%
Toxicology	3	1,4%
Pathology	0	0,0%
Human biology	0	0,0%
Total	214	100,0%

63.5% strongly agree that "research on human rights and sustainable development has a mostly positive effect on society"; a slightly higher consensus (69.2% strongly agree) on the statement "research on climate-related issues has a mostly positive effect on society". Similarly, 67.3% strongly agree that "Research on decent work, economic growth and the circular economy has a mostly positive effect on society", according to graph 45.

In this sense, the degree of agreement is higher (76.9% strongly agree) when assessing that "research on poverty reduction and food security has a positive effect on society". Three quarters of the sample strongly agreed with the statement that "research on affordable and clean energy has a mostly positive effect on society". Less agreement (on a broad consensus) is found for the idea that "research on a global agreement on Sustainable Development has a mostly positive effect on society", with 57.7% strongly agreeing and 32.7% agreeing.

Figure 43 : Degree of agreement with: Human Rights and Sustainable Development research has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 46 : Degree of agreement with: Research on poverty reduction and food security has a positive effect on society.

Figure 44 : Degree of agreement with: Research on climate-related issues has a mostly positive effect on society

Figure 47 : Degree of agreement with: Affordable and clean energy research has a mostly positive effect on society.

Graph 45 : Degree of agreement with: Research on decent work, economic growth and circular economy has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 48 : Degree of agreement with: Research on a global agreement on sustainable development has a mostly positive effect on society.

4. Part C

The link between political representation and scientific research is analysed through the following graphs. 41.7% somewhat agree, while 31.3% (strongly agree), with the statement that "Scientists and policy makers lack regular and well-supported opportunities to meet and exchange ideas. On the other hand, almost half of the sample (45.8%, neither agree nor disagree) do not express a consensus one way or the other on the idea that "researchers take appropriate initiatives to increase the acceptance of research by policy makers".

There is a greater consensus (35.4% strongly agree and 41.7% somewhat agree) that "insufficient funding of research structures and activities is the main obstacle in university policy", as shown in Figure 51. The degree of consensus is lower when assessing whether "researchers can expect recognition, reward and support for their work from employers, funders and peers", with 16.7% strongly agreeing and 29.2% somewhat agreeing.

Figure 49 : Degree of agreement with: Scientists and policy makers lack regular and well-supported opportunities to meet and exchange ideas

Figure 51 : Degree of agreement with: Insufficient funding of research structures and activities is the main obstacle to university policy.

Figure 50 : Degree of agreement with: Researchers take appropriate initiatives to increase the acceptance of research by policy makers.

Figure 52 : Degree of agreement with: Researchers can expect recognition, reward and support for their work from employers, funders and peer

In graph 53 we see a higher degree of consensus (45.8% strongly agree + 37.5% somewhat agree) when assessing that "policy makers and academics tend to have different priorities". There is also at least a significant consensus (31.3% strongly agree + 43.8% somewhat agree) on the idea that "socio-economic actors (e.g. local and regional businesses) and university policy makers often have different priorities".

Figure 56 shows agreement or disagreement with the fact that "researchers and socio-economic actors often have different priorities", with a higher degree of agreement (31.3% strongly agree and 45.8% somewhat agree). Whether "policy makers and socio-economic actors often have different priorities" also generates a similar consensus to the previous one from the sample

of the university community (29.2% strongly agree and 45.8% somewhat agree). 31% do not express any opinion (neither agree nor disagree) when assessing the fact that "researchers do research and science on issues relevant to society as a whole", while 39.6% reflect a certain degree of agreement (somewhat agree and 25% strongly agree).

Figure 53 : Degree of agreement with: Policy makers and academics tend to have different priorities

Figure 55 : Degree of agreement with: Policy makers and researchers tend to have different priorities

Figure 54 : Degree of agreement with: Socio-economic actors (e.g. local and regional businesses) and university policy makers often have different priorities.

Figure 56 : Degree of agreement with: Researchers and socio-economic actors tend to have different priorities

Figure 57 : Degree of agreement with: Political and socio-economic decision-makers tend to have different priorities

Figure 58 : Degree of agreement with: Researchers do research and science on topics relevant to society as a whole

5. Part E

In the following, the knowledge fields mentioned in the questionnaire are identified in the open-ended part of the questionnaire. For further details of the field involvement see table 10 with the literal specifications of the survey participants.

- Sustainability in relation to Food
- Recovery and Recycling of Materials.
- Recovery and Reuse of all kinds of products.
- Environmental Technology
- Education and Sustainability
- Collapse of biodiversity
- Agri-food sector
- Basic science outreach

Table 10 : Input on relevant research fields in which the EC2U Alliance could start to develop joint projects and Virtual Institutes

- Sostenibilidad en relación con los Alimentos. - Recuperación y Reciclaje de Materiales. - Aprovechamiento y Reutilización de todo tipo de productos. - Importancia de las Zoonosis. - Tecnología Medioambiental.

Hay muchas investigaciones sobre diversos campos sobre todo en educación y sostenibilidad, que no tienen ninguna repercusión en la sociedad. Investigar para resolver este problema sería prioritario

J'ai éprouvé des difficultés à me positionner sur les premières propositions concernant le poids de l'opinion publique, du politique et des acteurs socio-économiques sur les questions scientifiques. En effet, si je suis convaincu que ce poids doit être important, il faut que les acteurs soient informés sur les sujets de façon exhaustive et contradictoire avant d'établir un certain nombre de propositions (jurys-citoyens). Par ailleurs, il me semble qu'il existe un vrai décalage entre les objectifs fixés aux chercheurs par leurs tutelles (visibilité internationale, prestige, très long terme - en bref l'objectif type "Médaille aux jeux olympiques") et les besoins/attentes de la société sur des thèmes d'urgence (qualité de l'eau, effondrement de la biodiversité, question alimentaire...). Les chercheurs s'impliquant sur des thématiques de recherche-action sont même souvent "sanctionnés" dans leur avancement, cette recherche de terrain étant toujours considérée, en 2022, comme de seconde-catégorie par rapport aux "grandes questions". Un vrai travail de valorisation à faire à ce niveau, selon moi...

La información que llega a la sociedad sobre los temas de investigación y científicos en general suele ser parcial, fragmentada y en ocasiones contradictoria. Sería interesante desarrollar un programa de divulgación científica de base, con conceptos claros y no oportunistas.

No se pregunta en el temario sobre la implicación real de los investigadores de las universidades en los procesos de investigación de éstas; solo se pregunta sobre la existencia o no de infraestructuras / medios. Considero que la implicación de los distintos investigadores universitarios es muy diferente: existen casos de implicación desmedida y casos de ausencia de implicación desmedida. No se debería considerar a todos por igual para lo bueno o para lo malo, el "café para todos" no es bueno; cada uno debería tener una consideración proporcional a lo que de forma demostrable hace.

5. Analysis Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)

1. Technical sheet

The following table (Table 11) shows the completed questionnaires obtained in each of the parts.

Table 11 : Valid responses

Platform accesses	514
Questionnaires started	405
Completed questionnaires	
Part A	405
Part A + B	298 (5 incom.)
Part A + B + C	283
Part A + B + C + D	282
Part A + B + C + D + E	68

2. Part A

As in the previous section, the University of Salamanca is by far the one with the highest number of responses (63.2%) compared to others such as the University of Poitiers (15.1%) and the University of Iasi (10.6%).

Figure 59 : University of Origin

66.8% of respondents identify themselves as teaching staff with research duties, 9.4% as other teaching staff and 23.8% as researchers.

Figure 60 : Position within the university community

The research field of origin, as shown in table 12, with the greatest presence in the sample are the following: Humanities, Art and Literature (15.3%), Medical Sciences (9.2%), Linguistics (8.9%) or Biological Sciences (8.4%).

Table 12 : Field of research

	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	0	0,0%
Medical Sciences	37	9,2%
Linguistics	36	8,9%
Mathematics	14	3,5%
Technology	38	9,4%
Pedagogy	14	3,5%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	2	0,5%
Anthropology	3	0,7%
Political Science	2	0,5%
Physics	22	5,4%
Demography	0	0,0%
Psychology	19	4,7%
Chemistry	23	5,7%
Economic Sciences	24	5,9%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	62	15,3%
Biological Sciences	34	8,4%
Geography	4	1,0%
Sociology	11	2,7%
Space Sciences	10	2,5%
History	15	3,7%
Ethics	2	0,5%
Agricultural sciences	7	1,7%
Law and legal sciences	19	4,7%
Philosophy	6	1,5%
Total	404	100,0%

According to graph 61, the age of the respondents is varied: 60.6% are over 40 years old and 15.8% are between 20 and 30 years old, while 23.7% are between 30 and 40 years old. In terms of gender, 51.1% are female and 43.7% are male.

Figure 61 : Age range

Gráfico 3 : Gender

3. Part B

41% agreed and 39.6% disagreed on the following question related to public opinion, "public opinion should play an important role in guiding decisions on scientific issues"; the following statement also generated a certain polarisation towards one side or the other, with 45.6% agreeing and 31% disagreeing that "socio-economic actors should play an important role in guiding political decisions on scientific issues".

On the other hand, disagreement is higher 45.6% disagreement compared to agreement (32.9%) when it comes to assessing whether "political actors (local and regional government

bodies, political parties) should play an important role in guiding political decisions on scientific issues".

Figure 63 : Degree of agreement with: Public opinion has an important role to play in guiding decisions on scientific issues

Figure 65 : Degree of agreement with: Political actors (local and regional government bodies, political parties) have an important role to play in guiding policy decisions on science issues.

Figure 64 : Degree of agreement with: Socio-economic actors have an important role to play in guiding policy decisions on scientific issues.

Figure 66 : Degree of agreement with: Students should play an important role in identifying research topics relevant to society.

48% (29% somewhat agree) reflect a certain consensus when it comes to valuing "greater student participation in research topics relevant to society", while 23.5% do not define themselves.

As for the priority research topics for the near future, following the results in table 13, the most significant ones are: medical sciences (16.7%) and technology (11.8%).

Table 13 :Assessment of priority research topics for society in the near future (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	14	1,1%
Medical Sciences	219	16,7%
Linguistics	36	2,8%

Mathematics	38	2,9%
Technology	155	11,8%
Pedagogy	46	3,5%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	19	1,5%
Anthropology	21	1,6%
Political Science	23	1,8%
Physics	50	3,8%
Demography	30	2,3%
Psychology	60	4,6%
Chemistry	41	3,1%
Economic Sciences	58	4,4%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	75	5,7%
Biological Sciences	103	7,9%
Geography	10	0,8%
Sociology	28	2,1%
Space Sciences	67	5,1%
History	33	2,5%
Ethics	51	3,9%
Agricultural sciences	65	5,0%
Law and legal sciences	32	2,4%
Philosophy	35	2,7%
Total	1309	100,0%

The priority research fields at the university, according to the respondents, are, to a greater extent, medical sciences (15.2%), technology (10.8%), biological sciences (8.5%) and humanities (7.1%), according to table 14.

Table 14 : Assessment of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	17	1,4%
Medical Sciences	181	15,2%
Linguistics	59	4,9%
Mathematics	36	3,0%
Technology	129	10,8%
Pedagogy	42	3,5%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	10	0,8%
Anthropology	15	1,3%
Political Science	23	1,9%
Physics	58	4,9%
Demography	17	1,4%
Psychology	48	4,0%
Chemistry	42	3,5%

Economic Sciences	42	3,5%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	85	7,1%
Biological Sciences	101	8,5%
Geography	10	0,8%
Sociology	21	1,8%
Space Sciences	59	4,9%
History	38	3,2%
Ethics	34	2,8%
Agricultural sciences	50	4,2%
Law and legal sciences	48	4,0%
Philosophy	29	2,4%
Total	1194	100,0%

54.4% strongly agree and 27.6% somewhat agree with the following statement: "Research in Culture, Education and Languages has a mostly positive effect on society".

Figure 67 : Degree of agreement with: Research in Culture, Education and Languages has a mostly positive effect on society.

Four main fields of research should be given priority at university in the humanities for teachers and researchers: modern linguistics and lingua franca (11.0%), teacher training (10.2%), educational planning (10.5%) and cultural studies (10.5%).

Figure 68 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

Figure 69 : Degree of agreement with: Sustainability research has a mostly positive effect on society

Graph 69 shows the significant degree of agreement with the statement "Sustainability research has a mostly positive effect on society", while among the priority research fields, shown in the following graph (Graph 70), 14.9% point to environmental technology, 14.1% to climatology and 10.9% to agronomy.

Figure 70 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

85.4% strongly agree with the statement on health and research "Health research has a mostly positive effect on society".

Figure 71 : Degree of agreement with: Health research has a mostly positive impact on society

Table 15 lists the research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being: preventive medicine (10.7%), public health (9.5%) and neurosciences (9.3%) are the three most prominent topics.

Table 15: Rating of research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being research (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Psychology	114	8,7%
Pharmacodynamics	24	1,8%
Human physiology	32	2,5%
Clinical sciences	62	4,8%
Pharmacology	77	5,9%

Immunology	103	7,9%
Epidemiology	100	7,7%
Preventive medicine	139	10,7%
Microbiology	47	3,6%
Forensic sciences	5	0,4%
Psychiatry	45	3,4%
Molecular biology	58	4,4%
Occupational medicine	17	1,3%
Public health	124	9,5%
Virology	61	4,7%
Internal medicine	30	2,3%
Surgery	23	1,8%
Neurosciences	122	9,3%
Nutritional sciences	60	4,6%
Toxicology	19	1,5%
Pathology	15	1,1%
Human biology	28	2,1%
Total	1305	100,0%

60.8% strongly agree with the statement that "research on human rights and sustainable development has a mostly positive effect on society". The consensus is also significant (57.3% strongly agree) when it is stated that "research on climate-related issues has a mostly positive effect on society"; in the case of "research on decent work, economic growth and circular economy has a mostly positive effect on society", 69.3% strongly agree with this statement, as shown in graph 74.

Figure 72 : Degree of agreement with: Human Rights and Sustainable Development research has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 73 : Degree of agreement with: Research on climate-related issues has a mostly positive effect on society

Figure 74 : Degree of agreement with: Research on decent work, economic growth and circular economy has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 76: Degree of agreement with: Affordable and clean energy research has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 75 : Degree of agreement with: Research on poverty reduction and food security has a positive effect on society.

Figure 77 : Degree of agreement with: Research on a global agreement on sustainable development has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 75 "research on poverty reduction and food security has a positive effect on society" has 62.5% agreement (strongly agree). The same is true when respondents are asked how much they agree that "research on affordable and clean energy has a mostly positive effect on society" (Figure 76); In the last graph (Graph 77), in this section, the degree of agreement on whether "research on a global agreement for Sustainable Development has a mostly positive effect on society" was assessed, with a significant number of respondents (52.9%) strongly agreeing with this statement and 24% somewhat agreeing.

4. Part C

On the other hand, the first graph (Figure 78) in this section assesses the degree of agreement or disagreement as to whether "Scientists and policy makers lack regular and well-supported opportunities to meet and exchange ideas", with 36.7% strongly agreeing and 27.9% somewhat agreeing.

The degree of agreement is lower for the statement "Researchers take appropriate initiatives to increase the acceptance of research by policy makers", with 36.4% neither agreeing nor disagreeing and 26% disagreeing.

The next graph (Figure 80) assesses the degree of agreement or disagreement on the statement "insufficient funding of research structures and activities is the main obstacle in university policy", with a significant degree of agreement (77.1%), compared to the assessment of agreement on the statement "researchers can expect recognition, reward and support for their work from employers, funders and peers", with a lower 16.3% strongly agreeing and 20% somewhat agreeing.

Figure 78 : Degree of agreement with: Scientists and policy makers lack regular and well-supported opportunities to meet and exchange ideas.

Figure 79 : Degree of agreement with: Researchers take appropriate initiatives to increase the acceptance of research by policy makers.

Graph 80 : Degree of agreement with: Insufficient funding of research structures and activities is the main obstacle to university policy.

Figure 81 : Degree of agreement with: Researchers can expect recognition, reward and support for their work from employers, funders and peers.

In contrast (Figure 82), there is very significant agreement (61.1%, strongly agree and 27.9%, somewhat agree) on the statement "policy makers and academics often have different priorities". Consensus around agreement is lower for the following statement, "socio-economic

actors (e.g. local and regional businesses) and university policy makers often have different priorities", with more people somewhat agreeing (43%) than strongly agreeing (37.8%).

Figure 82 : Degree of agreement with: Policy makers and academics tend to have different priorities

Figure 83 : Degree of agreement with: Socio-economic actors (e.g. local and regional businesses) and university policy makers often have different priorities.

To conclude this section (Figure 84), 38.5% strongly agree and almost the same percentage (37.5%) somewhat agree with the statement "my research topic is very important and useful for society".

Figure 84 : Degree of agreement with: My research topic is very important and useful for the society.

5. Part D

In the following graph (Graph 85), the degree of agreement of those who completed the questionnaire is significant (49.6%, strongly agree and 31.6%, somewhat agree) with regard to the fact that "we need more international cooperation, for example, by participating in international research teams, to obtain better funding for our research", while the level of consensus or agreement is also significant (52.8%, strongly agree and 28.7%, somewhat agree), when the following question is asked, "taking part and participating actively in European research institutes will help us to promote our research".

In turn, in graph 87, we find a significant degree of agreement (61.7%) when evaluating the following statement, "the funds obtained in different national and international competitions are essential to advance in research", slightly lower than the degree of agreement (55.7%, very much in agreement) when evaluating, on the part of the people who responded to the survey.

Figure 85 : Degree of agreement with: We need more international cooperation, e.g. by participating in international research teams, to get better funding for our research.

Figure 87 : Degree of agreement with: Funds obtained in different national and international competitions are essential to advance research.

Figure 86 : Degree of agreement with: Being part of and actively participating in European research institutes will help us to boost our research.

Figure 88 : Degree of agreement with: Sharing research facilities and infrastructure among European universities is essential for high-quality research.

6. Part E

In the following, the knowledge fields mentioned in the questionnaire are identified in the open-ended questions section. For more detailed field involvement see table 16 with the literal specifications of the survey participants.

- Imbalances and marginalisation of rural areas in relation to urban areas
- Linguistic and cultural ecology and human rights; Linguistic and cultural ecology and sustainable development; Circular economy and climate change.
- Circular economy and climate change.

- Circular economy, energy efficiency, markets and quasi-markets.
- Physical exercise and health. Promotion of safe physical exercise.
- Humanities and social sciences
- Recovery, preservation and study of European cultural heritage.
- Gender studies
- Modern languages
- Ethics
- Cultural and Gender Studies
- Physics Energy and Photonics
- Educational Research and Programme Evaluation
- Equity and Education Systems
- Joint research with demographers, criminologists and economists
- Poverty and social exclusion
- Sustainability
- Preventive medicine
- Agricultural and agri-food technologies
- Human rights
- Heritage (architectural, artistic, cultural)
- Humanities and social sciences
- Sustainable chemistry
- Management sciences
- Multilingualism and translation

Table 16 : Inputs on relevant research fields in which the EC2U Alliance could start developing joint projects and Virtual Institutes

A better collaboration between public and private sectors in all fields of research due to the encountered challenges in Romania R&I system.

A ver si esto sirve para que se creen buenos grupos de investigación

Assurer les diversités : biologique, juridique, culturelle, pour agir au niveau global.

Aunque pertenezco al ámbito de Humanidades, creo que hay que primar los temas que redunden en mejorar la economía de España. Mucha investigación que veo que se hace, al menos en mi ámbito, es totalmente futil, inútil, son abstracciones y elucubraciones de ideas que no van a ningún sitio, excepto a engordar el CV de sus investigadores y así obtener cátedras. El dinero es muy limitado y debe empezar a crearse de una vez una jerarquía de prioridades para que la investigación sirva para algo. Actualmente no redundan en la economía española, somos el país que menos recibe a cambio del dinero gastado en investigación.

Bonjour, Je porte actuellement un projet en commun entre le laboratoire 4CS (Dr Bruno Constantin) de l'Université de Poitiers et le laboratoire Coimbra Chemistry Center (Prs Vitorino et Pais) de l'Université de Coimbra. C'est un projet transdisciplinaire qui vise à proposer de nouvelles formulations de médicaments sous forme de nanoparticules (U. Coimbra) et de les tester sur un modèle de mélanome (U. Poitiers). Nous espérons que ce projet sera soutenu par l'Université de Poitiers (appel à projet interne 2022 2IR UP-Squared, résultat en attente). Ce projet rentre dans le cadre des missions de l'Alliance UC2U (ODD "Santé et Bien-être") et nous aimerions un soutien pour mettre en place cette collaboration entre Coimbra et Poitiers et la développer. Cordialement, Julien Brillault

Creo que el sistema actual de métricas de medida de la calidad de la producción científica está viciado por su propia base. Se usan métodos y modos propios de finales del siglo XIX cuando la cantidad de científicos era muy inferior al actual. Sería muy interesante un Instituto que realmente intentara focalizarse en la medida del reconocimiento del esfuerzo científico y no en resultados "al peso de papel", mayormente trucados y basados en redes clientelares de confianza entre los investigadores de elite. Resulta increíble la producción científica anual de ciertas personas, pues no hay tiempo material para producir tanto. Para producir un resultado realmente revolucionario y relevante, muchos intentos tienen que quedar por el camino. Si no se premia este esfuerzo, lo único que se consigue es una producción abundante, aunque insulsa y de poco valor.

Desde la Universidad de Salamanca, de la que formo parte como investigadora en oncología, deberían centrarse en facilitar ayudas económicas a las personas que están cursando el doctorado. Me parece una vergüenza que no hayan concedido todas las becas de Ayuda para estancias en el extranjero para la mención de doctorado internacional y que no indiquen el criterio de selección de los alumnos, en concreto el criterio de evaluación de los currículums. En la convocatoria del 2022 hay disponibles 10 becas para Ciencias de la Salud, y solo han concedido 7. No facilitan NADA.

Desequilibrios y marginación de las zonas rurales en relación a las urbanas

Developper des nouvelles structures, instances, etc... est le cancer de la recherche. Cela entraine des mutations continuelles, des surcharges administratives, des budgets et personnels qui ne sont plus dans les laboratoires pour rien si ce n'est des chercheurs qui, une fois fini leurs heures statutaires, n'ont pas fait une minute de recherche en accomplissant que des taches qui ne correspondent pas à leur mission première.... il ne reste que les nuits et WE pour être a minima compétitif. Tout cela est hors sol, du vent, de la communication et totalement contre productif.

Difficile de choisir des priorités parmi les sciences à financer car aucune science ne peut avancer seule (ni géographie, ni chimie, ni mathématiques ni psychologie...) sans les apports des autres sciences... Toutes contribuent à construire les savoirs indispensables à la société.

Ecología lingüística y cultural y derechos humanos; Ecología lingüística y cultural y desarrollo sostenible

Economía circular y cambio climático.

Economía circular, eficiencia energética. mercados y cuasimercados, teoría de subastas

Ejercicio físico y salud. Promoción del ejercicio físico seguro.

El sesgo de la encuesta ya muestra la politización y la intervención de los poderes públicos en la orientación de la investigación universitaria. Antes era la utilidad lo que primaba en el reparto de fondos, ahora es el alineamiento con las tesis del pensamiento único, fuera del cual no existe ciencia, bien ni verdad. Lo que menos desean las instituciones es una Universidad independiente y crítica, que no esté al servicio de las tesis del poder. La renuncia al conocimiento de la identidad europea, que no aparece por ninguna parte en este cuestionario, es una muestra de cómo se supedita cualquier financiación a comulgar con los principios que informan el movimiento moderno (sostenibilidad, cambio climático, economía circular, etc.). Cualquier actividad fuera de ella es inútil o sospechosa.

El trabajo en identidad es útil tanto para estudios sobre literatura, para dar guías psicológicas que promuevan una mejor salud y para favorecer la igualdad de género. Además, se pueden aplicar a la educación estas temáticas

El valor de la ciudad como identidad europea

Es alarmante la ausencia de proyectos conjuntos entre Portugal y España. Los escasos fondos de los que disponen ambos países serían mejor empleados permitiendo compartir de manera activa los parquísimos medios de los que se dispone. De la arrumbada e infrafinanciada investigación en Humanidades prefiero ni hablar.

Es bien conocido que en cierto departamento había un sorprendente número de profesores con un éxito mundial reconocido (Nobel). En opinión de uno de ellos, esto se debía al café que consumían. Investigado el café, resultó ser regular (tirando a malo). Ahora bien, la cafetera estaba al fondo del departamento, y para llegar a ella era preciso atravesarlo, viendo lo que hacían los demás profesores. Esa parecía ser la causa del éxito: las conversaciones en el marco de la puerta, cinco minutos con un café en la mano. Propongo facilitar esa comunicación, quizá haciendo pequeñas comunicaciones menos formales y más orientadas a lo maravilloso del resultado que a hacer una nueva publicación.

Estos fondos sólo los aprovechan los paniaguados del Rector.

Estudios de género Lenguas modernas

Ética, Estudios Culturales y de Género, aplicación de los Estudios de Género al dominio social, político, literario, jurídico.

Física Energía Fotónica

Hace falta mayor compromiso decidido para co-financiar las tesis doctorales conjuntas de co-tutela en el ámbito de EC2U, sobre todo a las que ya están concedidas.

I really hope that the Virtual Institute will include a section dedicated to cultural heritage research.

I suggest creating an EC2UCafe institution for brainstorming. It would provide a small place to meet in each partner University, where staff (and selected students) from partner universities could discuss problems and solutions. Coffee included, easy terms for simple accommodation. Said problems including but not limited to a) the set up of international projects in small groups b) the required teaching in English of a number of credits, for all EC2U. c) the sharing of experience in small groups, such as giving counsel and asking for it I believe deeply that results would be very positive

I'd like to propose a study (or better a research agenda) on communication and its obstacles among academicians over different fields of specialization. Why so? There is a growing need to get to grips with the big picture in working for solutions to various kinds of vital issues facing the humanity at the moment. The research I propose would contribute to better figuring out what kind of a big picture the most relevant one would, indeed, be.

Investigación en Educación - Evaluación de Programas educativos - Equidad y sistemas educativos

Investigaciones conjuntas con demógrafos, criminólogos y economistas

J'aimerais avoir le temps pour réaliser une recherche davantage élargie au niveau européen, mais pour cela il faudrait EXPLICITEMENT libérer les enseignants-chercheurs (ce que je suis, en qualité de MCF Sciences de l'éducation et de la formation à l'Université de Poitiers) de leurs obligations administratives... Mes coordonnées : Stéphanie Netto stephanie.netto@univ-poitiers.fr Bonne analyse des données collectées dans cette enquête en ligne. Bien à vous, === Stéphanie Netto

Je suis dans le domaine de la microbiologie (recherche sur les amibes). Je serai très intéressé par d'éventuels projets communs.

Je travaille sur l'impact du changement climatique sur le rendement des plantes et je pense que cela va devenir un énorme challenge pour pouvoir continuer à nourrir la planète. Sélectionner des plantes moins demandeuses en eau et résilience vis à vis de la carence hydrique présente un challenge immense pour l'avenir de l'agriculture.

la chimie durable et la chimie du végétale

La investigación universitaria en España está sobrevalorada, Ni se hace, ni se realiza con coherencia investigadora, una gran mayoría lo hace por el tema económico de sexenios y así poder obtener la plaza de catedrático, en en el fondo los artículos y publicaciones están muy sobrevaloradas.

La mayoría de las preguntas están dirigidas a un resultado. Deben abandonarse los tópicos de las agendas de la ONU. La investigación debe evaluarse por resultados en distintos planos: Académico, profesional, social. Deben evitarse estructuras ajenas a la investigación Debe evitarse el planteamiento dialéctico en favor del positivista

La Organización es un aspecto clave en Investigación. Se deben establecer canales en los que los investigadores puedan intercambiar información de manera que se enriquezcan dichas investigaciones y se eviten duplicidades. Sería recomendable la creación de un órgano universitario (nacional o supranacional), que se dedicara a crear un repositorio con una doble perspectiva: investigación firme e investigación en proceso. De manera que se convierta en un elemento de coordinación que permita conseguir: 1. Mejores proyectos de investigación 2. Mejor aprovechamiento de los recursos destinados a investigación

La pandémie a eu des effets négatifs sur les contacts entre chercheurs qui ne se connaissent plus.

La pobreza, los colectivos excluidos y luchar contra la aporofobia, desde las instituciones y desde la sociedad. Pero sobre todo desde las instituciones. Criminalización de la pobreza y victimización por motivación aporófoba. Sinhogarismo y victimización. Programas de prevención del delito.

La priorité est l'emploi pour les jeunes chercheurs au service de la recherche en sciences humaines tout comme pour les recherches pluridisciplinaires qui de manière croissante impliquent les sciences humaines. Les financements sont trop souvent dédiés au fonctionnement ou à l'investissement et l'argent ne manque pas trop sur ce point. En revanche, la recherche SHES / Pluridisciplinaire a un besoin urgent de main d'œuvre.

La recherche est avant tout fondamentale et elle doit être libérée de toutes formes d'injonctions (politiques, économiques). La recherche est au service du bien commun. Ces principes sont la garantie d'une recherche créative et innovante.

Las preguntas de la encuesta estan mal diseñadas. Están orientadas. Muchas de ellas solo tienen una respuesta posible

Las preguntas sobre campos de investigación no deben reducirse a 5 opciones. Todo es necesario, por mi parte las daría como "nulas" El campo de la educación y psicología deberían potenciarse aún más

Les glycosciences, la science des sucres, est probablement le domaine de recherche le plus prometteur non seulement en chimie durable (valorisation de la biomasse constituée à 90% de sucres tels que la cellulose) mais aussi en santé (toutes nos cellules et celles des organismes pathogènes tels que virus et bactéries sont recouvertes de sucres; les sucres représentent la carte d'identité de nos cellules et une cellule cancéreuse aura un profil de sucres différent d'une cellule saine). C'est un domaine en plein essor avec des avancées thérapeutiques majeures ces dernières années.

Les sciences de gestion manquent à la liste de départ Sur le fond, le système académique contribue lui-même à enfermer les enseignants-chercheurs dans une bulle : pression à la publication dans des revues lues uniquement par des académiques, valorisation des publications au détriment de leur contribution à la société

Los estudios de Humanidades son esenciales para la formación integral de los individuos y el desarrollo de capacidades humanas que redundarán en la capacidad crítica para la toma de decisiones, algo absolutamente necesario para el desarrollo de las sociedades.

Materiales compuestos para los sectores del transporte y la biomedicina. Herramientas de simulación. Desarrollo de aplicaciones que permitan reducir el consumo energético

Me han parecido pocos los 5 temas o campos sobre los que es prioritario investigar. En mi opinión todo suma, no deberíamos olvidarnos de ningún tema porque todo es importante.

Medicina preventiva, salud pública y salud mental. Envejecimiento y calidad de vida. Energías limpias, gestión de recursos hídricos. Tecnologías agrícolas y agroalimentarias. Sostenibilidad, consumo, economía circular. Reciclaje y gestión de residuos, mitigación del cambio climático.

Necesitamos un instituto virtual de derechos humanos.

Patrimonio (arquitectónico, artístico, cultural)

Procesos de vulnerabilidad social y consecuencias psicosociales a quienes las padecen Victimizaciones derivadas de situaciones de vulnerabilidad social Políticas publicas y gobernanza para combatir la vulnerabilidad social

Recuperación, preservación y estudio del patrimonio cultural europeo

Research on the use of machine translation in different areas of life and occupations (not only translators), by laymen and professionals

Retos comunes (con matices diferentes según el contexto) relacionados con el multilingüismo, la inmigración, el racismo/xenofobia/etc, las nueva dinámicas sociales, la comunicación, entre otros.

Riesgos laborales relacionados con el avance tecnológico (automatización y digitalización) y con la descarbonización de la producción

Sería interesante un Instituto relacionado con el desarrollo de fármacos en diferentes campos de la terapéutica

Soziale und ökonomische Nachhaltigkeit

The research on Material sciences is in continue grow due to the request of new materials for electronic and medicine applications.

Two points that are missing: 1. fundamental research & 2. the implications of having a totally R&D orientend to industry. Deployment of (mathematical, physics and chemistry) models that do not have a quick implications are currently being put aside. Only direct application of R&D are being funded and it will lead in a recent future to lack of know-how and disruptive ideas for societal problems.

Very good that this kind of Alliance system is investigated further. The use of DNA in various fields, such as Molecular Ecology (~Ecological genetics) should be promoted. Also, collaboration between universities and research service enterprises (see e.g. www.bioname.fi) could be considered to make the research more cost-efficient.

Viendo que las líneas prioritarias de investigación suelen decantarse por la esfera de las ciencias puras, no estaría mal que se apoyara más la investigación en humanidades y ciencias sociales que permiten a las sociedades comprender mejor lo que han sido y lo que son y crear sociedades más justas.

Water management in agriculture (connecting social sciences, hydrology, climatology, agronomy)

6. Analysis Survey 4. Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes

1. Technical sheet

This first table (Table 17) shows the completed questionnaires relating to this chapter, as can be seen in the five parts.

Table 1 : Valid responses

Platform accesses	540
Questionnaires started	431
Completed questionnaires	
Parte A	431 (1 incomplete)
Parte A + B	334 (4 incomplete)
Parte A+B + C	312
Parte A + B + C + D	310 (1 incomplete)
Parte A + B + C + D + E	71

2. Part A

34.1% of those interviewed came, to a greater extent, from the University of Coimbra, 33.2% from the University of Salamanca, 16.5% from the University of Lasi and 11.8% from the University of Poitiers, as can be seen in the following graph (Graph 89).

Figure 89 : University of Origin

46.6% are teaching staff for research duties, 46.2% (other teaching staff) and 7.2% research.

Figure 90: Position within the university communiyt

Table 18 shows the fields of research from which the respondents came; most significantly, 11.9% from the Humanities, Arts and Literature, 10.7% from Technology and 9.1% from Medical Sciences.

Table 18 : Field of research

	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	2	0,5%
Medical Sciences	39	9,1%
Linguistics	16	3,7%
Mathematics	15	3,5%
Technology	46	10,7%
Pedagogy	17	4,0%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	1	0,2%
Anthropology	8	1,9%
Political Science	11	2,6%
Physics	23	5,3%
Demography	0	0,0%
Psychology	18	4,2%
Chemistry	22	5,1%
Economic Sciences	20	4,7%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	51	11,9%
Biological Sciences	34	7,9%
Geography	6	1,4%
Sociology	18	4,2%
Space Sciences	6	1,4%
History	15	3,5%
Ethics	6	1,4%
Agricultural sciences	12	2,8%
Law and legal sciences	37	8,6%
Philosophy	7	1,6%
Total	430	100,0%

43% of the respondents were between 20 and 30 years old and 30.5% between 30 and 40 years old, 44.4% were male and 52% female.

Figure 4 : Age range

Figure 5 : Gender

3. Part B

Half of the respondents in this section agree (more people "somewhat agree" than "strongly agree") that "public opinion should play an important role in guiding decisions on scientific issues"; on the other hand, 34% somewhat agree and 18.7% strongly agree when assessing the position of "socio-economic actors should play an important role in guiding political decisions on scientific issues".

Graph 95 assesses the link between political actors and scientific research, stating that "political actors (local and regional government bodies, political parties) should play an important role in guiding political decisions on scientific issues", 23% do not take a position (neither agree nor disagree), while 45.9% agree with this statement. There is greater consensus on whether "students should play an important role in identifying research topics relevant to society", with 40.8% somewhat agreeing and 44.4% strongly agreeing (Figure 96).

Figure 93 : Degree of agreement with: Public opinion has an important role to play in guiding decisions on scientific issues

Figure 95 : Degree of agreement with: Political actors (local and regional government bodies, political parties) have an important role to play in guiding policy decisions on scientific issues.

Figure 94 : Degree of agreement with: Socio-economic actors have an important role to play in guiding policy decisions on scientific issues.

Figure 96 : Degree of agreement with: Students should play an important role in identifying research topics relevant to society.

Table 19 identifies the assessment of the priority research topics for the future of society through a multi-response question; the two most frequently mentioned topics are medical sciences (14.5%), technology (11.5%) and pedagogy (6.7%); in the following table, the assessment of the main priority research fields in their university is noted, and the answers obtained again reflect medical sciences (12.1%), technology (10.7%) and pedagogy (6.1%).

Table 19 : Assessment of priority research topics for society in the near future (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	22	1,5%
Medical Sciences	220	14,5%
Linguistics	22	1,5%
Mathematics	35	2,3%
Technology	175	11,5%
Pedagogy	101	6,7%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	26	1,7%

Anthropology	27	1,8%
Political Science	51	3,4%
Physics	46	3,0%
Demography	19	1,3%
Psychology	95	6,3%
Chemistry	41	2,7%
Economic Sciences	70	4,6%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	60	4,0%
Biological Sciences	97	6,4%
Geography	15	1,0%

Sociology	58	3,8%
Space Sciences	57	3,8%
History	35	2,3%
Ethics	80	5,3%
Agricultural sciences	85	5,6%
Law and legal sciences	40	2,6%
Philosophy	40	2,6%
Total	1517	100,0%

Table 20 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	30	2,2%
Medical Sciences	163	12,1%
Linguistics	36	2,7%
Mathematics	39	2,9%
Technology	145	10,7%
Pedagogy	83	6,1%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	15	1,1%

Anthropology	27	2,0%
Political Science	47	3,5%
Physics	48	3,6%
Demography	13	1,0%
Psychology	79	5,8%
Chemistry	43	3,2%
Economic Sciences	58	4,3%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	74	5,5%
Biological Sciences	94	7,0%
Geography	17	1,3%
Sociology	44	3,3%
Space Sciences	50	3,7%
History	38	2,8%
Ethics	66	4,9%
Agricultural sciences	57	4,2%
Law and legal sciences	43	3,2%
Philosophy	42	3,1%
Total	1351	100,0%

Figure 97 : Degree of agreement with: Research in Culture, Education and Languages has a mostly positive effect on society.

More than half of the sample (55.3%) strongly agree that "research in Culture, Education and Languages has a mostly positive effect on society", and 26.1% somewhat agree.

The following graph (Figure 98) shows the fields of research that should be a priority at their university, with four of the options being the most frequently mentioned, firstly, educational theory and cultural studies (13.7%), followed by teaching (12.3%) and educational planning (12.3%).

Figure 98 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

The consensus is very significant (60.4% strongly agree and 27.6% somewhat agree) as to whether "sustainability research has a mostly positive effect on society". Among the main research fields (Figure 100), environmental technology (15.1%), climatology (14.3%) and agronomy (10.5%) are mentioned.

Figure 99 : Degree of agreement with: Sustainability research has a mostly positive effect on society

Figure 100 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

Figure 101 : Degree of agreement with: Health research has a largely positive impact on society

When asked whether "health research has a mostly positive effect on society", there is a general consensus, with 79.3% agreeing strongly and 15.6% agreeing somewhat.

The following table (Table 21) reflects the results derived from the question on which topics should be a priority in the field of health and well-being, starting with psychology (11.5%), preventive medicine (11%) and public health (10.8%).

Table 21 : Assessment of research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being research (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Psychology	172	11,5%
Pharmacodynamics	31	2,1%
Human physiology	65	4,3%
Clinical sciences	70	4,7%
Pharmacology	66	4,4%
Immunology	90	6,0%
Epidemiology	111	7,4%
Preventive medicine	165	11,0%

Microbiology	42	2,8%
Forensic sciences	14	0,9%
Psychiatry	77	5,1%
Molecular biology	55	3,7%
Occupational medicine	12	0,8%
Public health	162	10,8%
Virology	44	2,9%
Internal medicine	23	1,5%
Surgery	24	1,6%
Neurosciences	117	7,8%
Nutritional sciences	82	5,5%
Toxicology	16	1,1%
Pathology	18	1,2%
Human biology	43	2,9%
Total	1499	100,0%

When asked whether "research on human rights and sustainable development has a mostly positive effect on society", 60.7% of respondents in this section said they strongly agreed and 24.5% somewhat agreed. Similarly, there is general agreement (61.3% strongly agree and 26.6% somewhat agree) when it comes to the following statement, "research on climate-related issues has a mostly positive effect on society" (Figure 103).

Graph 104 shows the results of the respondents' assessment of whether "research on decent work, economic growth and the circular economy has a mostly positive effect on society", with 58.9% strongly agreeing and 23.9% somewhat agreeing. The statement on poverty reduction, "Research on poverty reduction and food security has a positive effect on society", is slightly more consensual (64.7% strongly agree and 22.4% somewhat agree).

Figure 106 assesses whether "research on affordable and clean energy has a mostly positive effect on society", with 64.4% strongly agreeing and 25.1% somewhat agreeing. The last graph in this section (Graph 107), "research on a global agreement on sustainable development has a mostly positive effect on society", generates a remarkable level of agreement. generates a remarkable level of agreement, with 51.4% agreeing strongly and 29.9% somewhat agreeing.

Figure 102 : Degree of agreement with: Human Rights and Sustainable Development research has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 105 : Degree of agreement with: Research on poverty reduction and food security has a positive effect on society.

Figure 103 : Degree of agreement with: Research on climate-related issues has a mostly positive effect on society

Figure 106: Degree of agreement with: Affordable and clean energy research has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 104 : Degree of agreement with: Research on decent work, economic growth and circular economy has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 107 : Degree of agreement with: Research on a global agreement on sustainable development has a mostly positive effect on society.

4. Part C

Figure 108 assesses the relationship between science and policy, with the following statement, "scientists and policy makers lack regular and well-supported opportunities to meet and exchange ideas", for which 3.9% strongly agree and 33.3% somewhat agree. The next statement generates a lower degree of agreement, "researchers take appropriate initiatives to

increase acceptance of research by policy makers", with only 28.5% agreeing somewhat, 38.8% disagreeing (neither agreeing nor disagreeing) and 23% disagreeing.

Figure 108 : Degree of agreement with: Scientists and policy makers lack regular and well-supported opportunities to meet and exchange ideas.

Figure 110 : Degree of agreement with: Insufficient funding of research structures and activities is the main obstacle in my research activities as a doctoral student.

Figure 109 : Degree of agreement with: Researchers take appropriate initiatives to increase the acceptance of research by policy makers.

Figure 111 : Degree of agreement with: Researchers and PhD students can expect recognition, reward and support for their work from employers, funders and peers.

In contrast, the following statement, "insufficient funding of research structures and activities is the main obstacle to my research activities as a doctoral student", with 46.5% agreeing (strongly agree) and 31.4% somewhat agreeing. And finally, when asked whether "researchers and doctoral students can expect recognition, reward and support for their work from employers, funders and colleagues", the answers are more varied, with more than half (54.5% agreement) agreeing, 21.4% disagreeing one way or the other and 24% disagreeing.

Figure 112 : Degree of agreement with: Policy-makers and researchers and doctoral students tend to have different priorities

In contrast to the previous statement, the present one, "policy makers and researchers and PhD students tend to have different priorities" generates a significant degree of agreement, with 52.6% strongly agreeing and 35.6% somewhat agreeing (Figure 112).

Figure 113 : Degree of agreement with: Socio-economic actors (e.g. local and regional businesses) and researchers and PhD students tend to have different priorities.

Figure 114 : Degree of agreement with: My doctoral topic is very important and useful for the society.

There is also agreement when assessing the fact that "socio-economic actors (e.g. local and regional companies) and researchers and doctoral students often have different priorities", as 41.3% somewhat agree, while 36.9% reaffirm this agreement (strongly agree).

The last graph in this section (Figure 114) is devoted to assessing the degree of agreement on "my doctoral subject is very important and useful for society", which reflects a significant consensus: 50.6% strongly agree and 33% somewhat agree.

5. Part D

This section links politics and science. Respondents (Figure 115) overwhelmingly support the area of international cooperation and scientific research. "We need more international cooperation, e.g. by participating in international research teams with other doctoral students and supervisors

from other countries, to get better funding for our research", a position to which 47% of the sample strongly agreed and 30.6% somewhat agreed.

Figure 115 : Degree of agreement with: We need more international cooperation, e.g. by participating in international research teams with other doctoral students and supervisors from other countries, in order to get better funding for our research.

Figure 117 : Degree of agreement with: Funds obtained in different national and international competitions are essential to advance research.

Figure 116 : Degree of agreement with: Being part of and actively participating in European research institutes will help me to acquire very important competences and boost our research.

Figure 118 : Degree of agreement with: Sharing research facilities and infrastructure among European universities is essential for high-quality research.

The agreement is even more significant with regard to the fact that "being part of and actively participating in European research institutes will help me to acquire very important competences and boost our research" (Figure 116), with 57% strongly agreeing and 26.8% somewhat agreeing.

Clearly, the need to obtain national and international funding is an unquestionable support for research, "funds obtained in different national and international competitions are essential to advance research" (Figure 117), as 58.9% (strongly agree) and 25.9% (somewhat agree) of respondents in this section state.

Support for research, in addition to funding, can be linked to the fact that "sharing research facilities and infrastructures between European universities is essential for high quality research",

as shown by the degree of agreement generated on this issue: 63.8% strongly agree and 27.2% somewhat agree.

Figure 119 : Degree of agreement with: Research and mobility programmes are essential to develop my doctoral research

Finally, more than half of the respondents in this section strongly agree (55%) or somewhat agree (24.9%) that "research programmes and mobility training are essential to develop my doctoral research".

6. Part E

In the following, the knowledge fields mentioned in the questionnaire are identified in the open-ended part of the questionnaire. For further details of the field involvement see table 22 with the literal specifications of the survey participants.

- Identity study/ identities and methodological fields in social sciences
- Artificial Intelligence
- Human rights
- Educational management
- Preventive health
- Migrations and inequality
- Psychology
- Educational sciences
- Agriculture and livestock farming
- Ethics of scientific research, argumentation and research methodology.
- Sport sciences
- Humanities

- Circular economy
- Taxation and fiscal area
- Information and knowledge management
- Socialisation and preservation of Cultural and Social Memory.
- Environmental Remediation
- Technological development
- Mathematical education.
- Linguistic and cultural diversity.
- Inter-European cooperation
- Social policie

Table 22 : Input on relevant research fields in which the EC2U Alliance could start to develop joint projects and Virtual Institutes

Estudio de la identidad/ las identidades y campos metodológicos en ciencias sociales

Creo que sería muy interesante potenciar el área de aplicación de la inteligencia artificial a proyectos de investigación que normalmente no se lo plantean, como por ejemplo los de estudios sociales de la Ciencia.

Siguientes temáticas:

las violaciones de los derechos humanos por la corrupción.

El uso de los nudges para la formación de los empleados públicos.

La prevaricación en España.

La falta de libertad de expresión en España contribuye a una menor transparencia y más corrupción.

Congresos científicos para estudiantes de doctorado.

Influencia de la Religión en las decisiones políticas de las élites.

Hay que aprovechar más oportunidades(intercambio, becas, subvenciones) para los estudiantes asiáticos doctorandos.

Gracias!

Sería útil proponer la concienciación sobre la problemática de la pérdida auditiva debido a la exposición prolongada al ruido en los objetivos de desarrollo sostenible.

Avanzar en estudios sobre investigación en comunicación

Gracias, los campos deben ser, la Educación rural en latinoamericana y el caribe. Esto es una pendiente, puesto que el fenómeno educativo de lo rural esta absolutamente limitado por las distancias de todo orden, político (Centralización), cultural (sesgo urbano), económico, sanitario, social, entre otros.

La evaluación como práctica pedagógica, es una pendiente.

La gestión educativa.

Es importante investigar en temas sanitarios que apunten al diagnóstico precoz de las enfermedades y a tratamiento efectivo, Además, en estudiar temas sociales relacionados a la migración, el hambre, la desigualdad y cómo desde la pedagogía se pueden comprender esos fenómenos.

La inteligencia artificial abordada de forma interdisciplinaria puede arrojar avances y resultados positivos en la comunidad, pero sería importante que no se trabaje de forma aislada en cada disciplina sino que haya una complementariedad por parte de las distintas instituciones e investigadores.

Creo que lo más relevante hoy por hoy es abrir el espacio Europeo a las comunidades y mediante alianzas intercontinentales, poner en valor la producción de conocimiento sudamericano, caribeño, africano, asiático, oceánico y norteamericano. Falta un diálogo y una comprensión menos eurocentrada en el desarrollo de la información y conocimiento. Es vital para los procesos de investigación.

Considero muy interesantes este tipo de estudios. Trabajar en equipo para impulsar el desarrollo de la ciencia y el bienestar social constituye una prioridad para todos. Muchas gracias.

Psicología

Valoro que se dé importancia a la educación, pero es un rótulo que sirve para hacer cualquier cosa. Estoy en contra del desvarío en educación al que asistimos. Espero que se refuercen las disciplinas, no que se vuelvan asignaturas mediocres en función de ideologías (buenas o malas, pero sí, seguro, pasajeras) .

AGENDA 2030: OBJETIVO 4 EDUCACIÓN DE CALIDAD. EDUCACIÓN PARA LA CIUDADANÍA GLOBAL (ECG). FORMACIÓN DEL PROFESORADO Y COMPETENCIAS DOCENTES

Se podría apoyar el intercambio de proyectos culturales entre las distintas universidades, promoviendo así la creación y el desarrollo artístico dentro de los campus. En Salamanca, que se precia de ser cuna de escritores del siglo de oro, hace falta un buen grupo de investigación o proyecto amplio dedicado a este ámbito que permita llevar a cabo buenas investigaciones al amparo de proyectos de largo alcance.

Producción y comercialización de productos procedentes de la agricultura y la ganadería , parece que los estados miembros se hacen la competencia entre sí, como Polonia y España en términos de producción de leche, en lugar de crear un servicio conjunto de comercialización de la misma para reducir el hambre en el planeta y conseguir precios justos para los productores.

Es importante enfatizar en formación sobre ética de la investigación científica, argumentación y metodología de la investigación. Formación en bioética, en todas las dimensiones y relaciones del ser humano con entorno biocultural y tecnocientífico permitirá profundizar en la reflexiones en torno a la dirección, intención y alcances del desarrollo tecnocientífico.

La promoción de la actividad física para la salud. La promoción del desarrollo de ciudades sostenibles. El fomento de competencias digitales docentes con enfoque crítico. La innovación en las estrategias de enseñanza a partir de tecnologías.

Sostenibilidad vital en la manera que tiene el individuo de consumir desde que nace hasta la edad adulta, economía circular en construcción-alimentación y ciclo del agua, nuevos métodos de contención de recursos hídricos, explotación de alimentos sostenibles medioambientalmente y para grandes grupos poblacionales.

Yo creo que debieran dedicar muchos más recursos al análisis del rol e importancia de las humanidades en el siglo XXI.

Área Tributaria y fiscal

Interdisciplina Científica y Humanística. Gestión de la Información y el conocimiento. Socialización y preservación de la Memoria Cultural y Social.

Temas relacionados con el empleo de la lingüística y su deriva actual, así como las relaciones de España con Hispanoamérica.

La investigación es una completa farsa.

Remediación del Medio Ambiente

Desarrollo tecnológico

Educación matemática.

Participo en una investigación internacional de interés nacional y tengo que tener 3 trabajos para poder comer. La pobreza del doctorado impide y retrasa los proyectos.

Estudios de la lengua e sociología.

- Diversidad lingüística y cultural.

Tiene que haber un mayor enfoque en los ODS, no en mantener el modo de vida de la sociedad actual que va muy alejado de ellos

-Cooperación inter-europea

-Políticas sociales

-Concienciación de la sociedad sobre investigación, cambio climático y nuevos desafíos

-Estudios culturales

El contexto de un estudiante de doctorado es complejo y variable en el tiempo, el solo enfocarse en terminar sus estudios ya es complicado. Realmente apoyarlo a que termine.

Además de todos los mencionados en la encuesta (tecnologías, ciencias de la salud, biología, química, etc.), un campo que considero importante es la enseñanza superior. Una formación de futuros docentes universitarios contribuirá, en mi opinión, a una educación e investigación de calidad en todos los sentidos.

Soy brasileño, vivo en Belém do Pará y mi tema de investigación científica es sobre la educación de los pueblos ribereños del municipio de Belém. En este estudio hago un contrapunto con los beneficios fiscales otorgados a las empresas, en especial a las mineras. Con una pregunta problema: ¿En qué medida impactan las concesiones de beneficios tributarios en las políticas públicas de educación básica de los pueblos ribereños?

Informatics and data analysis can form a core part of a virtual institute. Work in this area can aid most of the primary research fields like biology, physics, chemistry, sociology, ecology, etc. For example, bioinformatics, a subset of informatics, is a useful tool for all biological sciences. A virtual institute specializing in such computational sciences and data analysis can help create collaborations across disciplines, universities, societies, and countries.

Finantare suficienta pentru granturi

Colaborare intre universitati

Colaborare intre profesori straini si doctoranzi

TEOLOGIE

CRESTINISM

Necesar!

Mult succes și inspirație!

„Evoluția este cheia bunăstării,, - așa încât orice program de cercetare ce are impact pozitiv asupra societății și omului este binevenit.

Il est important de pouvoir mettre en œuvre les applications de certains type de recherche, et cela à une échelle suffisante pour avoir des résultats qui ne peuvent être ignorés par les politiciens et qui ne peuvent passer inaperçu aux yeux du public. Un exemple serait l'application de recherche conjointe entre plusieurs branches, dans le but de concevoir une ville "optimale" pour les habitants; et par la suite de la construire concrètement. Ce n'est qu'un exemple, mais il est fortement agaçant de voir certains problèmes sociétaux être discutés par le publique et les politiciens alors que la réponse fu apporté il y a des années par des scientifiques et que le tout est prouvés rigoureusement.

Veillez excusez les potentiels fautes et le probable dépassement des 300 mots.

Entendo que a ciência e a Inovação aberta são essenciais para o futuro das investigações e novas tecnologias. um exemplo disso foi a pandemia da COVID-19. Estreitar, intercambiar e acolher estudantes internacionais é estratégico para o alinhamento, o acumulo de competencias e novas parcerias em R&D e Inovação em todas as disciplinas e linhas de pesquisa. O estudante de doutoramento precisa muito conhecer novas fronteiras e novas equipe de investigação de sua linha de pesquisa, para aprimorar sua tese e seu conhecimentos e assim , compartilhar com a sociedade de modo que deem retorno para esta que ajuda a fortalecer as próprias universidades.

No further information. Thank u very much!

Tem que se terminar com a falta crónica de fundos atribuível às Ciências Sociais e Humanas, visto que:

- a) esta área é uma área de formação essencial na formação da personalidade humana;
- b) através do estudo de outros povos e culturas nós enriquecemos como pessoas e como sociedade;
- c) esquecer o passado é estar condenando a repeti-lo;
- d) por mais relevante que seja a área científica (matemática, química, medicina, etc.) sem fundamentos éticos de nada vale a ciência;
- e) olvidar as ciências sociais e humanas e remeter as mesmas para complementares, é um princípio errado, tendo em potencial o risco de ser disruptor das sociedades.

Ma thèse porte sur la "Participation du citoyen à l'action publique"

Problématique de démocratie participative d'actualité...

Nous sommes passés de 2 à 8 milliards d'êtres humains.

Environ 20 % sont dans des "démocraties"

Beaucoup de travail...

as common sensation in all my colleagues from my university and other European universities, working 3 or 4 years with a monthly salary of no more than 1.200 € is annoying when the cost os living is getting higher and higher because the political and humanitarian international crisis. As PhD students with a full time job, we are earning the same money as a truck/bus/taxi-driver but with 500% more stress and responsibilities.

Building multidisciplinary teams (mainly in low-income European countries) should be promoted, and overall the implementation of technological/digital methods in research. In these regions, there should be collaborations between the public (university) and the private sector (enterprises/corporations) where the researchers could acquire real-world/problem-solving skills.

Há poucas iniciativas, globalmente falando em comunicação de ciência. O doutorando comprometido com sua pesquisa quer divulgar o máximo possível. Entendo que há pouca divulgação também sobre os eventos realizados.

My suggestions are related to new approaches involving use cases of blockchain, smart contracts and non fungible tokens.

I just find it hard to develop a really great research without any grant or scholarship and having to work in random jobs part-time. Immigrants almost don't get the right to even apply for grants, only national students can, in most of local grants. This creates a difference due to economic factors that only rises the prejudice against immigrants, that end up having a lower performance in science, not because they are less skilled, but because they are in a disadvantaged situation. And being an immigrant and a single mother, it is nearly impossible, without the support of a grant. Science, as it is, it's still a privilege for just a few.

Penso que intercambios culturais e universitários entre países europeus e países da américa latina no sentido de aprofundamento de pesquisas empíricas na área da saúde em geral, economia sustentável e educação básica e em geral seriam ações de grande impacto positivo no desenvolvimento científico e social para as nações envolvidas. E, principalmente, uma grande meta seria fornecer conhecimentos e informações para subsidiar políticas públicas efetivas para a qualidade de vida dos cidadãos .

Tribology.

Solid lubricants.

Économie de la décroissance, Permaculture, Habitat écologique

I just want to put one question: how to integrate non-european researchers in european institutions?

I am developing an investigation related to the use of smart mobile devices for the management of personal knowledge in order to exponentiate infocommunicational behavior and I know that this is an important topic for the present and for the future of an increasingly connected society.

Global inequalities. It is necessary to impulse anti-patriarchal, anti-racist, anti-colonialist, and anti-capitalist efforts. Europe and the European universities need to more in changing the negative impacts they have in other parts of the planet. Building their "wealth" and "well-being" at the cost of others.

Critical Thinking being embedded in many key competences, a good subject for develop can be "How to develop Critical Thinking in higher education?" Every European country that want to develop Critical Thinking (CT) among his university students, they can develop instruments to measure CT. Moreover, they can develop relation with the Pedagogy researchers in order to develop reliable Teaching Strategy plans that can support, foster and develop CT.

I am glad that research on sustainability, agriculture, food, and energy are being spotlighted

In the field of Machine Learning/Artificial Intelligence, poorly funded universities lack the required hardware infrastructure needed to produce state-of-the-art research. Helping with acquiring such infrastructure or enabling sharing of it from more prominent universities is necessary if the EU is to be competitive with US/China in this field.

One relevant field of research that could be helped by joint projects refers to Linguistics of new or modern forms of politics and their different aims in the society.

Thank you!

Laboratory equipment should be more affordable for universities.

Toate domeniile sunt importante pentru a se realiza un echilibru in societate, dar ar trebui prioritizate in functie de gradul de influență asupra populației.

Votre questionnaire semble manquer de rigueur scientifique...

Je pense qu'il est plus pertinent de raisonner en termes d'intérêt général et de réponses à des besoins de la Société plutôt que disciplines

7. Analysis Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students

1. Technical sheet

Table 23 shows the survey sample, i.e. the respondents to each part of this survey among students and social interest groups.

Table 2 : Valid responses.

Platform accesses	404
Questionnaires started	292
Completed questionnaires	
Part A	292 (2 incomplete)
Part A + B	206 (2 incomplete)
Part A + B + C	193
Part A + B + C + E	30

2. Part A

63.7% of the respondents came from the University of Salamanca, 13.4% from the University of Iasi and 11.3% from the University of Poitiers as the most prominent universities.

Figure 120 : University of Origin

58.3% of the respondents were Bachelor's or Master's students, 38.3% were administrative and service staff and 3.4% were Alumni Service Directors.

Figure 121 : Position within the university community

Age is another of the variables analysed for the people who responded to this questionnaire; 49.8% are between 18 and 25 years of age and 39.2% are over 35 years of age. 32.6% are male and 65.6% are female.

Figure 122 : Age range

Figure 123 : Gender

3. Part B

To the 21.8% who strongly agree, we should add 29.1% (somewhat agree) when assessing whether "public opinion should play an important role in guiding decisions on scientific issues" (Figure 124); 37.9% somewhat agree with the idea that "socio-economic stakeholders should play an important role in guiding political decisions on scientific issues", and 18.9% strongly agree.

In this sense, "Political stakeholders (local and regional government bodies, political parties) should play an important role in guiding policy decisions on scientific issues", generates a certain level of consensus among respondents: 20.5% strongly agree and 25.9% somewhat agree. There is a significant degree of agreement on "students should play an important role in identifying research topics relevant to society", with 39% strongly agreeing and 36.6% somewhat agreeing (Figure 127).

Figure 124 : Degree of agreement with: Public opinion has an important role to play in guiding decisions on scientific issues

Figure 125 : Degree of agreement with: Socio-economic actors have an important role to play in guiding policy decisions on scientific issues.

Figure 126 : Degree of agreement with: Political stakeholders (local and regional government bodies, political parties) have an important role to play in guiding political decisions on scientific issues.

Figure 127 : Degree of agreement with: Students should play an important role in identifying research topics relevant to society.

The priority research topics for students and social interest groups are as follows, as shown in the following table of responses (Table 24): medical sciences (14.8%) and technology (11.3%) are the two chosen topics, in addition to psychology with 7.1%.

And, in terms of the research fields that should have priority at their university, again, medical sciences (14.1%) and technology (10.2%) are the chosen ones, together with psychology (6.7%).

Table 24 : Assessment of priority research topics for society in the near future (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	16	1,8%
Medical Sciences	135	14,8%
Linguistics	35	3,8%
Mathematics	30	3,3%
Technology	103	11,3%
Pedagogy	44	4,8%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	22	2,4%
Anthropology	12	1,3%
Political Science	18	2,0%
Physics	28	3,1%
Demography	18	2,0%
Psychology	65	7,1%
Chemistry	23	2,5%
Economic Sciences	43	4,7%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	50	5,5%
Biological Sciences	41	4,5%
Geography	12	1,3%
Sociology	20	2,2%
Space Sciences	53	5,8%
History	16	1,8%
Ethics	41	4,5%
Agricultural sciences	33	3,6%
Law and legal sciences	34	3,7%
Philosophy	20	2,2%
Total	912	100,0%

Table 25 : Assessment of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	18	2,2%
Medical Sciences	117	14,1%
Linguistics	55	6,6%
Mathematics	35	4,2%
Technology	85	10,2%
Pedagogy	31	3,7%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	12	1,4%
Anthropology	9	1,1%
Political Science	21	2,5%
Physics	25	3,0%
Demography	8	1,0%
Psychology	56	6,7%
Chemistry	18	2,2%
Economic Sciences	37	4,5%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	53	6,4%
Biological Sciences	41	4,9%
Geography	12	1,4%
Sociology	20	2,4%
Space Sciences	42	5,1%
History	19	2,3%
Ethics	30	3,6%
Agricultural sciences	25	3,0%
Law and legal sciences	45	5,4%
Philosophy	17	2,0%
Total	831	100,0%

On the other hand, 53.7% strongly agree that "research in Culture, Education and Languages has a mostly positive effect on society" and 27.8% somewhat agree.

Figure 128 : Degree of agreement with: Research in Culture, Education and Languages has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 129 reflects the assessment of the main research fields that should be prioritised at their university, of which the following stand out; linguistics and modern languages (13.4%), teaching (10.3%), educational planning (11.1%) and cultural studies (10.8%).

Figure 129 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

The statement, "sustainability research has a mostly positive effect on society" generates a high level of consensus, with 61% strongly agreeing and 23.9% somewhat agreeing (Figure 130).

Figure 130 : Degree of agreement with: Sustainability research has a mostly positive effect on society

Figure 131 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-response: maximum five options)

With regard to the research fields that should be prioritised at their university, the answers point mainly to climatology (13.6%), environmental technology (13.4%) and the economics of climate change (10.2%), while there is some consensus on whether "health research has a mostly positive effect on society", with 77.5% strongly agreeing and 17.6% somewhat agreeing.

Figure 132 : Degree of agreement with: Health research has a mostly positive impact on society

Table 26 : Assessment of research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being research (Multi-response: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage
Psychology	108	11,7%
Pharmacodynamics	17	1,8%
Human physiology	23	2,5%
Clinical sciences	36	3,9%
Pharmacology	52	5,6%
Immunology	84	9,1%
Epidemiology	76	8,2%
Preventive medicine	84	9,1%
Microbiology	34	3,7%
Forensic sciences	5	0,5%
Psychiatry	62	6,7%
Molecular biology	27	2,9%
Occupational medicine	12	1,3%
Public health	76	8,2%
Virology	38	4,1%
Internal medicine	10	1,1%
Surgery	31	3,3%
Neurosciences	53	5,7%
Nutritional sciences	48	5,2%
Toxicology	14	1,5%
Pathology	10	1,1%
Human biology	26	2,8%
Total	926	100,0%

The research topics related to health and well-being that should be a priority, according to the responses obtained in the following table (Table 26), are, in this order, psychology (11.7%), immunology (9.1%) and preventive medicine (9.1%).

53.9% strongly agree and 31.9% agree with the statement that "research on human rights and sustainable development has a mostly positive effect on society" (Figure 133); 57.8% strongly agree and 28.4% agree with the statement "research on climate-related issues has a mostly positive effect on society".

Figure 133 : Degree of agreement with: Human Rights and Sustainable Development research has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 136 : Degree of agreement with: Research on poverty reduction and food security has a positive effect on society.

Figure 134 : Degree of agreement with: Research on climate-related issues has a mostly positive effect on society

Figure 137: Degree of agreement with: Affordable and clean energy research has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 135 : Degree of agreement with: Research on decent work, economic growth and circular economy has a mostly positive effect on society.

Figure 138 : Degree of agreement with: Research on a global agreement on sustainable development has a mostly positive effect on society.

4. Part C

63.7% agree (strongly agree + somewhat agree) with the statement that "scientists and policy makers lack regular and well-supported opportunities to meet and exchange ideas"; 36.3% neither agree nor disagree, while 47.7% agree with the statement that "researchers take appropriate initiatives to increase the acceptance of research by policy makers".

50.3% strongly agree (strongly agree) and 34.7% (somewhat agree) on "insufficient funding of research structures and activities is the main obstacle in university policy", and less on whether "researchers can expect recognition, reward and support for their work from employers, funders and peers", with 19.2% strongly agreeing and 32.1% somewhat agreeing, while 27.5% did not express an opinion.

Figure 139 : Degree of agreement with: Scientists and policy makers lack regular and well-supported opportunities to meet and exchange ideas.

Figure 141 : Degree of agreement with: Insufficient funding of research structures and activities is the main obstacle to university policy.

Figure 140 : Degree of agreement with: Researchers take appropriate initiatives to increase the acceptance of research by policy makers.

Figure 142 : Degree of agreement with: Researchers can expect recognition, reward and support for their work from employers, funders and peers.

Graph 143 shows the degree of agreement with the statement "politicians and academics tend to have different priorities", which is significant, as 60% strongly agree with this statement and 29.5% somewhat agree.

Figure 143 : Degree of agreement with: Policy makers and academics tend to have different priorities

Figure 144 : Degree of agreement with: Socio-economic actors (e.g. local and regional businesses) and researchers tend to have different priorities.

Figure 145 : Degree of agreement with: Policy makers and researchers tend to have different priorities

Finally, graph 144 assesses the degree of agreement or consensus on whether "socio-economic actors (e.g. local and regional companies) and researchers tend to have different priorities", which is remarkable, at least in that 37.3% agree strongly and 41.5% somewhat agree; and finally, before moving on to conclusions and contributions, with regard to the degree of agreement on whether "policy makers and researchers often have different priorities", 25.9% disagreed (neither agreeing nor disagreeing), 32.1% disagreed and 42% agreed with this statement.

5. Part E

In the following, the knowledge fields mentioned in the questionnaire are identified in the open questions section. For further details of the field involvement see table 27 with the literal specifications of the survey participants.

- Climate change.
- Education and Language Teaching
- Renewable Energy Development
- Citizen Awareness Programmes on Sustainable Development
- Interactions in the history of literature between authors belonging to different universities.
- Psychoanalysis, and its application to current education systems
- Sustainability projects

- New forms of mobility
- Biodiversity and endangered species
- Humanities and social sciences

Table 27 : Input on relevant research fields in which the EC2U Alliance could start to develop joint projects and Virtual Institutes

Me gustaría que se avanzara en investigación médica y sobre el cambio climático.

Las Universidades no deben olvidar la investigación básica, siempre perjudicada a la hora de recibir financiación, sin embargo sin esta, la investigación aplicada sería imposible además de ser la piedra angular para la formación de nuevos investigadores.

Según mi criterio la relación investigación-sociedad deja mucho que desear. Es imperiosamente necesario hacer cuantas actuaciones sean necesarias (información, campañas, divulgación, cursos, etc.) para concienciar a los ciudadanos, que la investigación es necesaria para el bienestar y desarrollo de la humanidad. Si esta relación no se mejora, nunca habrá una financiación digna en la investigación.

Educación y Enseñanza de Idiomas

Salud (prevención de pandemias, promover proyectos de investigación en todos los campos de la medicina), Emergencia Climática, Estudio del problema de la Emigración. Desarrollo Energías Renovables, Nuevos cultivos. Programas de concienciación ciudadana sobre el Desarrollo Sostenible, etc.

Entre investigación, necesidades y su relación con la política y economía existen muchos intereses creados fuera del control de las capacidades de los investigadores. Un buen tema de estudio sería la involución de la sociedad: causas y consecuencias. Gracias

Sería interesante realizar un estudio conjunto de las interacciones de la historia de la literatura entre autores pertenecientes a las diferentes universidades

Psicoanálisis, y su aplicación a los sistemas de educación actual, podría cambiar la forma de educar y por ende la sociedad resultante.

Proyectos de sostenibilidad, más estudios de conservación ambiental y de utilización inteligente de los recursos, más estudios antropológicos e inserción social así como de inclusión.

Sustainability and climate change should be number one at this point.

How to make people consume less?

Intuyo que este cuestionario va a ser importante a la hora de decidir presupuestos. Ningún departamento necesita menos dinero, todos necesitan más medios, personal y financiación. Aunque no me parezca relevante un área de investigación, no significa que no tenga valor social. En concreto, Humanidades es una gran potencia en Salamanca, pero no se valora todo lo que debería al ser de Letras.

2GM

Debido a la reciente pandemia, considero que una de las propuestas más necesarias es la relacionada con los aspectos virológicos de las enfermedades, para así poder prevenirlas en lugar de pasar de nuevo por una crisis de la misma naturaleza y magnitud.

Ninguno. Que abandonen la idea de institutos virtuales y en cambio abaraten los costes de matrícula y créditos en las Universidades de verdad.

Energías renovables

Medicină, istorie contemporană

Sobre lingüística

Me parecería muy interesante que en una universidad se enseñara a los alumnos sobre las nuevas tecnologías que van a venir de cara a un futuro ya que el día de mañana es lo que estará en vigor en cualquier ámbito.

Sa începem sa investim energie și timp in viitorul nostru!

Este nevoie de personal calificat.

Este nevoie ca politicienii sa se implice mai mult.

Pentru a crea o lume mai buna si pentru ca tehnologia sa nu distruga ceea ce era autentic.

Este nevoie de proiecte umanitare nu sa se imbogateasca cineva ...

Nuevas forma de movilidad para vehículos como baaterías, gas e hidrogeno

No tengo mucho que aportar aquí debido a que desconocía este proyecto de alianza. Me alegro de que exista y les deseo los mejores resultados.

En lengua y literatura clásica tanto latín y griego como la de cada país se debe profundizar; hay que saber bien de dónde vienes para poder mejorar tu camino hacia donde vas. Otro punto fuerte de la alianza debería ser el estudio de enfermedades neurodegenerativas o el cáncer para poder encontrar soluciones cuanto antes.

En el ámbito estudiantil en el que yo personalmente convivo con cientos de personas jóvenes, una de las mayores tendencias en cuanto a salud es la ansiedad y la depresión. Además, he podido conocer muchos casos de jóvenes con padres maltratadores tanto física como psicológicamente y me resulta indispensable un estudio sobre como el entorno tanto familiar como educacional es relevante en los resultados académicos de los jóvenes y sus repercusiones en el ámbito de salud mental.

- Maneras en las que se puedan modificar las grandes empresas y vehículos para contrarrestar el efecto invernadero.

- Ayudas para investigar especies en peligro de extinción y luchar contra ello, colaborando con reservas o concienciando Gobiernos.

- Eventos para que la gente ayude a limpiar las playas.

It should be noted that even in Europe the countries are very different in various aspects (political, economical, environmental, societal etc.). Therefore, it may be difficult to determine important areas of research. It should also be considered that different fields of study or research may have both positive and negative effects. For example, if we investigate the effect of environmental or human right issues, these may cause strong disagreements between various parties and public. It is important to be cautious with delicate issues. It was also somewhat difficult to answer the questions in the survey because it was not explained what is meant with different fields which can be interpreted in different ways across Europe. For example, with medical sciences we tend to think about medicine and education of doctors, a field that is already heavily funded. But, sometimes there are also minor fields within medical faculties, which are somewhat neglected and underfunded. These minor fields should be acknowledged and better funded. They could have bigger impact on both science and society that is currently considered.

Some of the questions were quite absurd. For example, it is not possible to select five priorities for one's university regarding the fields of science. In addition the fields were quite odd, not familiar or recognizable in my county.

Les hommes politiques n'écotent pas assez l'opinion publique. Les acteurs socio-économiques ne pensent qu'aux intérêts économiques.

La recherche médicale reste prioritaire, et ensuite se focaliser sur le climat, l'empreint carbone.

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035803

Survey on R&I Needs of EC2U Alliance

Results Annex

I. Methodology and technical sheet

In this social study, the target population/universe was the university community and social agents linked to the following universities:

- University of Coimbra
- University of Iasi
- University of Jena
- University of Pavia
- University of Poitiers
- University of Salamanca
- University of Turku

The sample design or sampling technique refers to how the sample is selected from the aforementioned population. In the study we present, a non-probabilistic sampling technique is chosen, characterised by the following characteristics:

1. The choice of the elements is not random, but conveniently chosen at the discretion of the researcher himself.
2. It is not possible to estimate the sampling error.

In the present study we can speak of two complementary types of sampling, on the one hand, convenience sampling, since specific population segments have been selected for the collection of information; and on the other hand, snowball sampling, characterised by the possibility of accessing the survey through third party mailings.

The data collection technique was carried out using the CAWI (Computer Assisted Web Interviewing) system, by means of e-mails and distribution of links with access to the data collection platform. The online platform used is LIMESURVEY, developers of the open source survey software, facilitating data security and transparency in data collection.

Incidents and problems in data collection have meant that there are significant differences in the participants from the different universities. Differences in school calendars and summer holidays have notably affected participation. Despite the difficulties encountered, a segmentation of the sample by universities has been established in order to observe whether there are notable and/or opposing differences. In order to counteract the surveys with the lowest response rates, the following analysis scheme has been established:

- A. Exporting the data for each university according to the segment of the university community at which it was aimed (See S1 - S2 - S3 - S4 and S5).
- B. Preliminary analysis of the results and selection of the independent variables included in the specific analyses. In a first exploration, it is observed that the 1-5 scale variables linked to the degree of agreement with specific statements, no significant differences are detected between the different universities and the general overall result presented in the previous report. Due to this circumstance, the analysis of the following variables is proposed:
 - a. Identification of relevant research fields for the future EC2U Virtual Research Institutes.
 - b. Contribution of relevant research fields to initiate joint projects in future EC2U Virtual Research Institutes.
 - c. Generation of a new variable called total overall sum per university, grouping the answers of all the segments participating in the survey linked to the variables specified above and forming part of the analysis.
 - d. Creation of graphical figures for the variables that allow it and with total results for the university.

II. University of Coimbra

In this first section and following Table 1, we can see the distribution of the sample obtained at the University of Coimbra (177 questionnaires) for each of the five questionnaires carried out in this study. Each of the questionnaires was addressed to a specific group: 40.4% of the total belongs to the group of University Managers (Survey 1); Questionnaire 2 is addressed to political and socio-economic agents (2.2%); Questionnaire 3 is addressed to research and teaching staff (3.6%); Questionnaire 4, with the highest representation, is addressed to doctoral students (53.1%) and Questionnaire 5 to students and agents interested in research (0.7%).

Table 1: Distribution of the sample according to the survey

	Frequency	Percentage
Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)	112	40,4%
Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)	6	2,2%
Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)	10	3,6%
Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes	147	53,1%
Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students	2	0,7%
Total	277	100,0%

Graphically, we can see the distribution of the sample and the groups that responded most according to the type of questionnaire at the University of Coimbra: Postgraduate Students (53.1%) and University Managers (40.4%).

Figure 1 : Distribution of the sample according to the survey

With regard to priority research topics for the future, another of the objectives addressed in the study, the responses (a maximum of five responses per questionnaire) reflect a certain trend when analysing the combined results of all the questionnaires; firstly, both medical science and technology are the most frequently mentioned topics, and secondly, biology and agronomy appear as priority topics for the future. It should be noted, on the other hand, that in questionnaire 5, the results are reversed and both astronomy and astrology and anthropology appear, by far, as the most important subjects for the future.

Table 2 : Assessment of priority research topics for society in the near future (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	5	1,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	5	1,0%	1	33,3%	11	1,1%
Medical Sciences	43	11,0%	1	5,3%	6	16,2%	71	13,9%	0	0,0%	121	12,6%
Linguistics	5	1,3%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	5	1,0%	0	0,0%	11	1,1%
Mathematics	12	3,1%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	1	0,2%	0	0,0%	14	1,5%
Technology	32	8,2%	4	21,1%	7	18,9%	65	12,7%	0	0,0%	108	11,2%
Pedagogy	27	6,9%	1	5,3%	1	2,7%	29	5,7%	0	0,0%	58	6,0%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	4	1,0%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	5	1,0%	1	33,3%	11	1,1%
Anthropology	7	1,8%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	10	2,0%	1	33,3%	18	1,9%
Political Science	14	3,6%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	27	5,3%	0	0,0%	41	4,3%
Physics	9	2,3%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	5	1,0%	0	0,0%	15	1,6%
Demography	15	3,8%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	5	1,0%	0	0,0%	21	2,2%
Psychology	16	4,1%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	35	6,8%	0	0,0%	52	5,4%
Chemistry	6	1,5%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	6	1,2%	0	0,0%	13	1,3%
Economic Sciences	10	2,6%	1	5,3%	2	5,4%	28	5,5%	0	0,0%	41	4,3%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	24	6,1%	1	5,3%	1	2,7%	16	3,1%	0	0,0%	42	4,4%
Biological Sciences	26	6,6%	2	10,5%	5	13,5%	36	7,0%	0	0,0%	69	7,2%
Geography	9	2,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	8	1,6%	0	0,0%	17	1,8%
Sociology	14	3,6%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	27	5,3%	0	0,0%	42	4,4%
Space Sciences	15	3,8%	4	21,1%	3	8,1%	19	3,7%	0	0,0%	41	4,3%
History	26	6,6%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	18	3,5%	0	0,0%	45	4,7%
Ethics	27	6,9%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	27	5,3%	0	0,0%	54	5,6%
Agricultural sciences	21	5,4%	3	15,8%	4	10,8%	38	7,4%	0	0,0%	66	6,9%
Law and legal sciences	9	2,3%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	9	1,8%	0	0,0%	19	2,0%
Philosophy	16	4,1%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	17	3,3%	0	0,0%	33	3,4%
Total	392	100,0%	19	100,0%	37	100,0%	512	100,0%	3	100,0%	963	100,0%

Table 3 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	6	1,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	7	1,5%	1	33,3%	14	1,6%
Medical Sciences	39	10,7%	2	10,5%	7	18,4%	61	13,0%	0	0,0%	109	12,2%
Linguistics	7	1,9%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	6	1,3%	0	0,0%	14	1,6%
Mathematics	10	2,8%	0	0,0%	3	7,9%	3	0,6%	1	33,3%	17	1,9%
Technology	31	8,5%	3	15,8%	7	18,4%	57	12,1%	1	33,3%	99	11,1%
Pedagogy	21	5,8%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	18	3,8%	0	0,0%	39	4,4%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	5	1,4%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	3	0,6%	0	0,0%	9	1,0%
Anthropology	7	1,9%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	10	2,1%	0	0,0%	17	1,9%
Political Science	12	3,3%	0	0,0%	1	2,6%	27	5,7%	0	0,0%	40	4,5%
Physics	7	1,9%	0	0,0%	2	5,3%	10	2,1%	0	0,0%	19	2,1%
Demography	8	2,2%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	4	0,9%	0	0,0%	13	1,5%
Psychology	15	4,1%	0	0,0%	1	2,6%	27	5,7%	0	0,0%	43	4,8%
Chemistry	4	1,1%	0	0,0%	1	2,6%	11	2,3%	0	0,0%	16	1,8%
Economic Sciences	16	4,4%	1	5,3%	2	5,3%	25	5,3%	0	0,0%	44	4,9%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	39	10,7%	1	5,3%	1	2,6%	23	4,9%	0	0,0%	64	7,2%
Biological Sciences	9	2,5%	2	10,5%	5	13,2%	40	8,5%	0	0,0%	56	6,3%
Geography	8	2,2%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	9	1,9%	0	0,0%	17	1,9%
Sociology	15	4,1%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	23	4,9%	0	0,0%	38	4,3%
Space Sciences	12	3,3%	4	21,1%	4	10,5%	13	2,8%	0	0,0%	33	3,7%
History	24	6,6%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	18	3,8%	0	0,0%	42	4,7%
Ethics	23	6,3%	0	0,0%	1	2,6%	24	5,1%	0	0,0%	48	5,4%
Agricultural sciences	14	3,9%	3	15,8%	2	5,3%	23	4,9%	0	0,0%	42	4,7%
Law and legal sciences	16	4,4%	0	0,0%	1	2,6%	12	2,6%	0	0,0%	29	3,2%
Philosophy	15	4,1%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	16	3,4%	0	0,0%	31	3,5%
Total	363	100,0%	19	100,0%	38	100,0%	470	100,0%	3	100,0%	893	100,0%

The study also made it possible to assess the opinion of the different agents linked to the University of Coimbra with regard to the fields of research that should be a priority at their own university. Two are the priority fields (see table 3) with the greatest consensus: medical science (12.2%) and technology (11.1%) and, at a greater distance, below 10%, are economic science, humanities, arts and literature.

Table 4 presents the results with regard to the question of priority research fields at the University, although different subjects emerge from the previous item, since the priority field indicated is cultural studies (15.9%), followed by teaching (14.1%), educational research (12.6%) and educational theory (12%).

Table 4: Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Linguistics and modern languages	18	5,1%	1	6,3%	2	5,4%	25	5,5%	1	33,3%	47	5,4%
Modern History	30	8,5%	0	0,0%	3	8,1%	24	5,3%	0	0,0%	57	6,6%
Classical languages and linguistics	8	2,3%	0	0,0%	3	8,1%	9	2,0%	0	0,0%	20	2,3%
Ancient and Medieval History	17	4,8%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	15	3,3%	0	0,0%	32	3,7%
Modern Literature	12	3,4%	1	6,3%	2	5,4%	10	2,2%	0	0,0%	25	2,9%
Anthropology	24	6,8%	1	6,3%	5	13,5%	38	8,4%	1	33,3%	69	8,0%
Theory of literature	8	2,3%	1	6,3%	0	0,0%	9	2,0%	1	33,3%	19	2,2%
Ethnography and ethnology	26	7,3%	2	12,5%	3	8,1%	28	6,2%	0	0,0%	59	6,8%
Education theory	38	10,7%	2	12,5%	3	8,1%	61	13,4%	0	0,0%	104	12,0%
Cultural studies	62	17,5%	2	12,5%	3	8,1%	70	15,4%	0	0,0%	137	15,9%
Educational planning	36	10,2%	2	12,5%	5	13,5%	66	14,5%	0	0,0%	109	12,6%
Teaching	46	13,0%	4	25,0%	6	16,2%	66	14,5%	0	0,0%	122	14,1%
Contemporary history	29	8,2%	0	0,0%	2	5,4%	33	7,3%	0	0,0%	64	7,4%
Total	354	100,0%	16	100,0%	37	100,0%	454	100,0%	3	100,0%	864	100,0%

The following graph (Graph 2) shows, specifically, an average of the total results, already noted in the previous table (last column) of all the questionnaires carried out, where we have already shown

how cultural studies and teaching were the priority fields of research with the greatest consensus in the case of the University of Coimbra.

Figure 2 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university
(Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

Concern for climate change and the transformation of the economic development model towards sustainability and the circular economy are shown in the topics chosen as priorities in the following table, when analysing the results obtained in the five surveys, especially in those with a higher volume of responses.

Table 5 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequenc	Percentag	Frequenc	Percentag	Frequenc	Percentag	Frequenc	Percentag	Frequenc	Percentag	Frequenc	Percentag
	y	e	y	e	y	e	y	e	y	e	y	e
Atmospheric Sciences	25	7,0%	0	0,0%	4	10,8%	29	6,0%	1	50,0%	59	6,6%
Meteorology	5	1,4%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	18	3,7%	0	0,0%	23	2,6%
Climatology	44	12,4%	3	15,8%	4	10,8%	67	13,9%	0	0,0%	118	13,2%
Oceanography	48	13,5%	2	10,5%	3	8,1%	61	12,6%	0	0,0%	114	12,7%
Geochemistry	1	0,3%	0	0,0%	3	8,1%	7	1,4%	0	0,0%	11	1,2%
Agronomy	28	7,9%	3	15,8%	5	13,5%	49	10,1%	0	0,0%	85	9,5%
Geodesy	4	1,1%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	5	1,0%	0	0,0%	10	1,1%
Physics	7	2,0%	0	0,0%	2	5,4%	13	2,7%	0	0,0%	22	2,5%
Geography	18	5,1%	1	5,3%	1	2,7%	13	2,7%	1	50,0%	34	3,8%
Environmental Technology	54	15,2%	3	15,8%	7	18,9%	75	15,5%	0	0,0%	139	15,5%
Geology	9	2,5%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	5	1,0%	0	0,0%	15	1,7%
Economics of technological change	34	9,6%	0	0,0%	2	5,4%	50	10,4%	0	0,0%	86	9,6%
Geophysics	4	1,1%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	7	1,4%	0	0,0%	11	1,2%
Circular economy	45	12,7%	3	15,8%	4	10,8%	48	9,9%	0	0,0%	100	11,2%
Hydrology	29	8,2%	2	10,5%	2	5,4%	36	7,5%	0	0,0%	69	7,7%
Total	355	100,0%	19	100,0%	37	100,0%	483	100,0%	2	100,0%	896	100,0%

The total results shown in the table above, when assessing the five questionnaires, are shown in the graph below; environmental technology (15.5%), climatology (13.2%), oceanography (12.7%) and circular economy (11.2%) are the topics most frequently mentioned by the different groups in the study linked to the University of Coimbra.

Figure 3 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

The following table (Table 6) shows the topics that should have the highest priority in the field of health and well-being according to the opinions collected in the different questionnaires, with three of them standing out (more than 10%) with respect to the rest: public health (12.2%), preventive medicine (11.3%) and psychology (10.1%).

Table 6 : Assessment of research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being research (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Psychology	33	8,7%	1	7,1%	2	5,3%	57	11,5%	1	33,3%	94	10,1%
Pharmacodynamics	8	2,1%	1	7,1%	3	7,9%	15	3,0%	0	0,0%	27	2,9%
Human physiology	10	2,6%	0	0,0%	2	5,3%	22	4,4%	0	0,0%	34	3,7%
Clinical sciences	21	5,6%	0	0,0%	2	5,3%	29	5,8%	0	0,0%	52	5,6%
Pharmacology	15	4,0%	0	0,0%	2	5,3%	21	4,2%	0	0,0%	38	4,1%
Immunology	20	5,3%	1	7,1%	2	5,3%	23	4,6%	0	0,0%	46	5,0%
Epidemiology	29	7,7%	1	7,1%	1	2,6%	40	8,1%	0	0,0%	71	7,6%
Preventive medicine	44	11,6%	1	7,1%	4	10,5%	56	11,3%	0	0,0%	105	11,3%
Microbiology	5	1,3%	2	14,3%	2	5,3%	14	2,8%	1	33,3%	24	2,6%
Forensic sciences	1	0,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	7	1,4%	1	33,3%	9	1,0%
Psychiatry	26	6,9%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	20	4,0%	0	0,0%	46	5,0%
Molecular biology	7	1,9%	1	7,1%	2	5,3%	22	4,4%	0	0,0%	32	3,4%
Occupational medicine	10	2,6%	0	0,0%	1	2,6%	3	0,6%	0	0,0%	14	1,5%
Public health	51	13,5%	0	0,0%	3	7,9%	59	11,9%	0	0,0%	113	12,2%
Virology	12	3,2%	2	14,3%	0	0,0%	20	4,0%	0	0,0%	34	3,7%
Internal medicine	4	1,1%	1	7,1%	1	2,6%	8	1,6%	0	0,0%	14	1,5%
Surgery	5	1,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%		0,0%	0	0,0%	5	0,5%
Neurosciences	34	9,0%	1	7,1%	6	15,8%	34	6,9%	0	0,0%	75	8,1%
Nutritional sciences	21	5,6%	2	14,3%	3	7,9%	22	4,4%	0	0,0%	48	5,2%
Toxicology	4	1,1%	0	0,0%	1	2,6%	3	0,6%	0	0,0%	8	0,9%
Pathology	1	0,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	8	1,6%	0	0,0%	9	1,0%
Human biology	17	4,5%	0	0,0%	1	2,6%	13	2,6%	0	0,0%	31	3,3%
Total	378	100,0%	14	100,0%	38	100,0%	496	100,0%	3	100,0%	929	100,0%

Finally, in this last table, we include the contributions made (open question) in the different questionnaires carried out at the University of Coimbra by means of an open question included in each of the questionnaires:

Table 7 : Contributions on the relevant research fields in which the EC2U Alliance could start developing joint projects and Virtual Institutes

Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)

Bridge Natural Sciences and Human and Social Sciences
service management (tourism and leisure)
culture and heritage studies
Territorial cohesion
ERRADICAÇÃO DA FOME
Economía Circular
Antropología do cuidado
Ciências do desporto
Humanidades e Artes o investimento económico internacional

Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)

No contributions

Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)

No contributions

Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes

Ciências Sociais e Humanas,
Políticas públicas
Solid lubricants

Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students

No contributions

III. University of Iasi

The total sample obtained at the University of Iasi, when adding up the responses obtained in each of the five questionnaires, amounts to 171 questionnaires. Questionnaire 3, questionnaire 4 and questionnaire 5 are the ones with the highest number of responses, with 43 teacher-researchers (25.1%) in questionnaire 3, 71 doctoral students (41.5%) in questionnaire 4, and 40 students and interested staff (23.4%) in questionnaire 5.

Table 8: Distribution of the sample according to the survey

	Frequency	Percentage
Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)	15	8,8%
Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)	2	1,2%
Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)	43	25,1%
Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes	71	41,5%
Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students	40	23,4%
Total	171	100,0%

Graphically, we can see below (Graph 4), the volume (%) of responses obtained in each of the questionnaires with respect to the total number of responses obtained at the University of Iasi (171 questionnaires).

Figure 4 : Distribution of the sample according to the survey

Three are the most chosen research topics for society in the near future, according to the responses in the table below (Table 9); firstly, medical science (14.1%), secondly, technology (10.8%) and, below 10% of the total responses, life sciences (8.2%).

Table 9 : Assessment of priority research topics for society in the near future (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	0,6%	4	1,6%	3	2,9%	8	1,4%
Medical Sciences	9	14,3%	1	10,0%	21	13,3%	38	15,4%	13	12,4%	82	14,1%
Linguistics	1	1,6%	0	0,0%	2	1,3%	6	2,4%	2	1,9%	11	1,9%
Mathematics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	1,3%	5	2,0%	3	2,9%	10	1,7%
Technology	4	6,3%	2	20,0%	17	10,8%	29	11,8%	11	10,5%	63	10,8%
Pedagogy	2	3,2%	1	10,0%	5	3,2%	19	7,7%	6	5,7%	33	5,7%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	1	1,6%	0	0,0%	5	3,2%	7	2,8%	6	5,7%	19	3,3%
Anthropology	1	1,6%	0	0,0%	2	1,3%	6	2,4%	1	1,0%	10	1,7%
Political Science	1	1,6%	1	10,0%	3	1,9%	0	0,0%	2	1,9%	7	1,2%
Physics	2	3,2%	0	0,0%	9	5,7%	10	4,1%	3	2,9%	24	4,1%
Demography	2	3,2%	1	10,0%	3	1,9%	3	1,2%	6	5,7%	15	2,6%
Psychology	6	9,5%	0	0,0%	4	2,5%	12	4,9%	5	4,8%	27	4,6%
Chemistry	1	1,6%	0	0,0%	6	3,8%	9	3,7%	3	2,9%	19	3,3%
Economic Sciences	2	3,2%	1	10,0%	13	8,2%	12	4,9%	6	5,7%	34	5,8%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	2	3,2%	0	0,0%	4	2,5%	6	2,4%	0	0,0%	12	2,1%
Biological Sciences	6	9,5%	0	0,0%	18	11,4%	20	8,1%	4	3,8%	48	8,2%
Geography	2	3,2%	0	0,0%	5	3,2%	2	0,8%	3	2,9%	12	2,1%
Sociology	2	3,2%	2	20,0%	4	2,5%	8	3,3%	4	3,8%	20	3,4%
Space Sciences	5	7,9%	0	0,0%	7	4,4%	10	4,1%	5	4,8%	27	4,6%
History	1	1,6%	0	0,0%	5	3,2%	3	1,2%	3	2,9%	12	2,1%
Ethics	4	6,3%	0	0,0%	7	4,4%	13	5,3%	6	5,7%	30	5,2%
Agricultural sciences	5	7,9%	1	10,0%	11	7,0%	15	6,1%	5	4,8%	37	6,4%
Law and legal sciences	1	1,6%	0	0,0%	1	0,6%	7	2,8%	4	3,8%	13	2,2%
Philosophy	3	4,8%	0	0,0%	3	1,9%	2	0,8%	1	1,0%	9	1,5%
Total	63	100,0%	10	100,0%	158	100,0%	246	100,0%	105	100,0%	582	100,0%

Life sciences (8.9%), technology (7.9%) and pedagogy (7.1%) are the priority subjects at the University of Lasi, although none of these subjects is rated higher than 10%.

Table 10 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	2	3,4%	0	0,0%	2	1,4%	4	2,1%	4	4,5%	12	2,4%
Medical Sciences	1	1,7%	1	10,0%	8	5,6%	15	7,7%	3	3,4%	28	5,7%
Linguistics	3	5,1%	0	0,0%	2	1,4%	7	3,6%	4	4,5%	16	3,2%
Mathematics	3	5,1%	0	0,0%	2	1,4%	6	3,1%	4	4,5%	15	3,0%
Technology	4	6,8%	1	10,0%	12	8,3%	17	8,8%	5	5,7%	39	7,9%
Pedagogy	2	3,4%	1	10,0%	7	4,9%	21	10,8%	4	4,5%	35	7,1%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	1	1,7%	0	0,0%	3	2,1%	3	1,5%	2	2,3%	9	1,8%
Anthropology	2	3,4%	0	0,0%	3	2,1%	5	2,6%	1	1,1%	11	2,2%
Political Science	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	1,4%	3	1,5%	3	3,4%	8	1,6%
Physics	3	5,1%	0	0,0%	13	9,0%	10	5,2%	2	2,3%	28	5,7%
Demography	1	1,7%	2	20,0%	3	2,1%	3	1,5%	2	2,3%	11	2,2%
Psychology	4	6,8%	0	0,0%	4	2,8%	10	5,2%	9	10,2%	27	5,5%
Chemistry	4	6,8%	0	0,0%	10	6,9%	8	4,1%	4	4,5%	26	5,3%
Economic Sciences	2	3,4%	2	20,0%	9	6,3%	10	5,2%	5	5,7%	28	5,7%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	4	6,8%	0	0,0%	4	2,8%	5	2,6%	0	0,0%	13	2,6%
Biological Sciences	3	5,1%	1	10,0%	17	11,8%	18	9,3%	5	5,7%	44	8,9%
Geography	3	5,1%	0	0,0%	6	4,2%	3	1,5%	3	3,4%	15	3,0%
Sociology	2	3,4%	1	10,0%	3	2,1%	5	2,6%	3	3,4%	14	2,8%
Space Sciences	4	6,8%	0	0,0%	11	7,6%	4	2,1%	5	5,7%	24	4,8%
History	3	5,1%	0	0,0%	7	4,9%	2	1,0%	5	5,7%	17	3,4%
Ethics	4	6,8%	1	10,0%	5	3,5%	15	7,7%	6	6,8%	31	6,3%
Agricultural sciences	1	1,7%	0	0,0%	7	4,9%	9	4,6%	0	0,0%	17	3,4%
Law and legal sciences	1	1,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	7	3,6%	8	9,1%	16	3,2%
Philosophy	2	3,4%	0	0,0%	4	2,8%	4	2,1%	1	1,1%	11	2,2%
Total	59	100,0%	10	100,0%	144	100,0%	194	100,0%	88	100,0%	495	100,0%

The priority research fields at the University of Lasi, according to the results obtained in Table 11, are especially linked, as at the University of Coimbra, to the field of education, educational theory and languages.

Table 11: Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Linguistics and modern languages	8	13,6%	1	10,0%	12	8,5%	26	13,0%	8	9,5%	55	11,1%
Modern History	4	6,8%	1	10,0%	9	6,4%	6	3,0%	3	3,6%	23	4,7%
Classical languages and linguistics	4	6,8%	0	0,0%	6	4,3%	15	7,5%	4	4,8%	29	5,9%
Ancient and Medieval History	3	5,1%	0	0,0%	9	6,4%	3	1,5%	3	3,6%	18	3,6%
Modern Literature	0	0,0%	1	10,0%	8	5,7%	12	6,0%	8	9,5%	29	5,9%
Anthropology	6	10,2%	0	0,0%	10	7,1%	11	5,5%	5	6,0%	32	6,5%
Theory of literature	1	1,7%	0	0,0%	4	2,8%	4	2,0%	4	4,8%	13	2,6%
Ethnography and ethnology	4	6,8%	0	0,0%	9	6,4%	13	6,5%	5	6,0%	31	6,3%
Education theory	6	10,2%	2	20,0%	18	12,8%	23	11,5%	11	13,1%	60	12,1%
Cultural studies	7	11,9%	2	20,0%	16	11,3%	23	11,5%	11	13,1%	59	11,9%
Educational planning	4	6,8%	1	10,0%	14	9,9%	22	11,0%	8	9,5%	49	9,9%
Teaching	8	13,6%	2	20,0%	20	14,2%	32	16,0%	10	11,9%	72	14,6%
Contemporary history	4	6,8%	0	0,0%	6	4,3%	10	5,0%	4	4,8%	24	4,9%
Total	59	100,0%	10	100,0%	141	100,0%	200	100,0%	84	100,0%	494	100,0%

As shown graphically in Figure 5, teaching (14.6%) is the most chosen priority research field out of the five possible answers, followed by educational theory (12.1%), cultural studies (11.9%) and linguistics and modern languages (11.1%).

Figure 5 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

In the following table (Table 12) we note the results related to the priority research fields (University of Lasi), both for each of the surveys and for the total, as we have been doing throughout the report, and from the results, it can be seen that the themes related to sustainability, climate change and the transformation of the economic development model are the most selected.

Table 12 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequenc	Percentag	Frequenc	Percentag	Frequenc	Percentag	Frequenc	Percentag	Frequenc	Percentag	Frequenc	Percentag
	y	e	y	e	y	e	y	e	y	e	y	e
Atmospheric Sciences	4	7,4%	0	0,0%	14	10,7%	20	9,7%	9	10,0%	47	9,6%
Meteorology	4	7,4%	1	10,0%	8	6,1%	12	5,8%	5	5,6%	30	6,1%
Climatology	7	13,0%	2	20,0%	16	12,2%	31	15,0%	13	14,4%	69	14,1%
Oceanography	1	1,9%	0	0,0%	8	6,1%	9	4,4%	5	5,6%	23	4,7%
Geochemistry	2	3,7%	0	0,0%	6	4,6%	1	0,5%	5	5,6%	14	2,9%
Agronomy	4	7,4%	2	20,0%	13	9,9%	26	12,6%	8	8,9%	53	10,8%
Geodesy	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	0,8%	1	0,5%	3	3,3%	5	1,0%
Physics	3	5,6%	0	0,0%	7	5,3%	9	4,4%	3	3,3%	22	4,5%
Geography	2	3,7%	0	0,0%	4	3,1%	6	2,9%	4	4,4%	16	3,3%
Environmental Technology	11	20,4%	1	10,0%	21	16,0%	31	15,0%	7	7,8%	71	14,5%
Geology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	1,5%	5	2,4%	5	5,6%	12	2,4%
Economics of technological change	6	11,1%	2	20,0%	11	8,4%	21	10,2%	10	11,1%	50	10,2%
Geophysics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	4	3,1%	5	2,4%	1	1,1%	10	2,0%
Circular economy	7	13,0%	2	20,0%	9	6,9%	14	6,8%	6	6,7%	38	7,7%
Hydrology	3	5,6%	0	0,0%	7	5,3%	15	7,3%	6	6,7%	31	6,3%
Total	54	100,0%	10	100,0%	131	100,0%	206	100,0%	90	100,0%	491	100,0%

In fact, following on from the previous table, four priority research fields stand out, as shown graphically below: environmental technology (14.5%), climatology (14.1%), agronomy (10.8%) and the economics and technology of change (10.2%).

Figure 6 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

The main topics that should have the highest priority in the field of health and wellbeing at the University of Lasi, according to the responses received (Table 13) are the following: preventive medicine (11.4%), public health (8.8%) and psychology (8.1%).

Table 13 : Assessment of research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being research (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Psychology	5	7,6%	1	10,0%	8	5,3%	24	10,3%	9	7,7%	47	8,1%
Pharmacodynamics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	3	2,0%	1	0,4%	5	4,3%	9	1,6%
Human physiology	5	7,6%	0	0,0%	5	3,3%	19	8,2%	7	6,0%	36	6,2%
Clinical sciences	4	6,1%	1	10,0%	11	7,3%	10	4,3%	6	5,1%	32	5,5%
Pharmacology	2	3,0%	1	10,0%	6	4,0%	8	3,4%	3	2,6%	20	3,5%
Immunology	9	13,6%	1	10,0%	10	6,6%	16	6,9%	14	12,0%	50	8,7%
Epidemiology	6	9,1%	2	20,0%	14	9,3%	17	7,3%	11	9,4%	50	8,7%
Preventive medicine	6	9,1%	2	20,0%	20	13,2%	26	11,2%	12	10,3%	66	11,4%
Microbiology	1	1,5%	0	0,0%	3	2,0%	8	3,4%	8	6,8%	20	3,5%
Forensic sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	0,7%	1	0,4%	1	0,9%	3	0,5%
Psychiatry	1	1,5%	0	0,0%	2	1,3%	7	3,0%	4	3,4%	14	2,4%
Molecular biology	2	3,0%	0	0,0%	8	5,3%	3	1,3%	2	1,7%	15	2,6%
Occupational medicine	2	3,0%	0	0,0%	3	2,0%	3	1,3%	2	1,7%	10	1,7%
Public health	4	6,1%	2	20,0%	18	11,9%	24	10,3%	3	2,6%	51	8,8%
Virology	2	3,0%	0	0,0%	8	5,3%	5	2,1%	6	5,1%	21	3,6%
Internal medicine	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	0,7%	4	1,7%	3	2,6%	8	1,4%
Surgery	2	3,0%	0	0,0%	3	2,0%	3	1,3%	3	2,6%	11	1,9%
Neurosciences	6	9,1%	0	0,0%	11	7,3%	22	9,4%	3	2,6%	42	7,3%
Nutritional sciences	2	3,0%	0	0,0%	8	5,3%	22	9,4%	6	5,1%	38	6,6%
Toxicology	2	3,0%	0	0,0%	3	2,0%	3	1,3%	2	1,7%	10	1,7%
Pathology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	0,7%	2	0,9%	2	1,7%	5	0,9%
Human biology	5	7,6%	0	0,0%	4	2,6%	5	2,1%	5	4,3%	19	3,3%
Total	66	100,0%	10	100,0%	151	100,0%	233	100,0%	117	100,0%	577	100,0%

The contributions obtained (Table 14) in the different questionnaires are listed in the following table:

Table 14 : Contributions on the relevant research fields in which the EC2U Alliance could start developing joint projects and Virtual Institutes

Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)

Sociologie
Psihologie
Neurostiinte

Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)

No contributions

Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)

Cultural heritage research
Material sciences

Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes

Critical Thinking
Machine Learning/Artificial Intelligence
TEOLOGIE

Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students

Medicină
Istorie contemporanăSa

IV. University of Jena

First of all, it should be noted that the total sample obtained at the University of Jena does not allow for a certain socio-statistical representativeness of the different actors to whom each of the five questionnaires is addressed. In total, 35 responses were obtained.

Table 15: Distribution of the sample according to the survey

	Frequency	Percentage
Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)	8	22,9%
Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)	6	17,1%
Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)	5	14,3%
Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes	2	5,7%
Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students	14	40,0%
Total	35	100,0%

The highest level of response was obtained in Questionnaire 5, the one addressed to students and interested staff (14 responses, 40%), followed by Questionnaire 1 (university managers, 22.9% : 8 responses), socio-political and economic agents (17.1%) and teachers/researchers (14.3%).

Figure 7 : Distribution of the sample according to the survey

The priority research topics in society for the near future are medical science, linguistics and sociology, which account for 10% or more of the responses.

Table 16 : Assessment of priority research topics for society in the near future (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage										
Logic	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Medical Sciences	1	5,9%	3	15,8%	2	14,3%	0	0,0%	5	13,5%	11	12,2%
Linguistics	1	5,9%	2	10,5%	3	21,4%	1	33,3%	4	10,8%	11	12,2%
Mathematics	2	11,8%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	3	8,1%	5	5,6%
Technology	3	17,6%	1	5,3%	1	7,1%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	5	5,6%
Pedagogy	0	0,0%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	1	33,3%	3	8,1%	5	5,6%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	33,3%	1	2,7%	2	2,2%
Anthropology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Political Science	1	5,9%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	3	8,1%	4	4,4%
Physics	1	5,9%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,2%
Demography	1	5,9%	1	5,3%	1	7,1%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	3	3,3%
Psychology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	7,1%	0	0,0%	2	5,4%	3	3,3%
Chemistry	0	0,0%	2	10,5%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	3	3,3%
Economic Sciences	0	0,0%	1	5,3%	1	7,1%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,2%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	1	5,9%	0	0,0%	1	7,1%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,2%
Biological Sciences	1	5,9%	1	5,3%	1	7,1%	0	0,0%	3	8,1%	6	6,7%
Geography	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	1	1,1%
Sociology	2	11,8%	3	15,8%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	4	10,8%	9	10,0%
Space Sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	7,1%	0	0,0%	2	5,4%	3	3,3%
History	1	5,9%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	5,4%	4	4,4%
Ethics	0	0,0%	1	5,3%	2	14,3%	0	0,0%	2	5,4%	5	5,6%
Agricultural sciences	0	0,0%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	2	2,2%
Law and legal sciences	1	5,9%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,1%
Philosophy	1	5,9%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,1%
Total	17	100,0%	19	100,0%	14	100,0%	3	100,0%	37	100,0%	90	100,0%

Medical science (12.9%) and linguistics (10.8%) are the research fields that should be given priority at the University, as can be seen in the following table (Table 17).

Table 17 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage										
Logic	1	5,6%	1	5,3%	2	13,3%	1	25,0%	2	5,4%	7	7,5%
Medical Sciences	1	5,6%	2	10,5%	1	6,7%	1	25,0%	7	18,9%	12	12,9%
Linguistics	2	11,1%	2	10,5%	2	13,3%	1	25,0%	3	8,1%	10	10,8%
Mathematics	1	5,6%	0	0,0%	1	6,7%	1	25,0%	1	2,7%	4	4,3%
Technology	0	0,0%	1	5,3%	1	6,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,2%
Pedagogy	1	5,6%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	3	3,2%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	2	11,1%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,2%
Anthropology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	6,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,1%
Political Science	0	0,0%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	4	10,8%	5	5,4%
Physics	1	5,6%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,1%
Demography	1	5,6%	1	5,3%	1	6,7%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	4	4,3%
Psychology	0	0,0%	1	5,3%	1	6,7%	0	0,0%	2	5,4%	4	4,3%
Chemistry	1	5,6%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,2%
Economic Sciences	0	0,0%	1	5,3%	1	6,7%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	3	3,2%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	2	11,1%	0	0,0%	1	6,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	3	3,2%
Biological Sciences	1	5,6%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	4	10,8%	6	6,5%
Geography	0	0,0%	2	10,5%	1	6,7%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	4	4,3%
Sociology	1	5,6%	2	10,5%	1	6,7%	0	0,0%	4	10,8%	8	8,6%
Space Sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	1	1,1%
History	1	5,6%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,2%
Ethics	0	0,0%	1	5,3%	1	6,7%	0	0,0%	3	8,1%	5	5,4%
Agricultural sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Law and legal sciences	1	5,6%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	2	2,2%
Philosophy	1	5,6%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	2,7%	2	2,2%
Total	18	100,0%	19	100,0%	15	100,0%	4	100,0%	37	100,0%	93	100,0%

The research fields that should be given priority at the University of Jena are, taking into account the limitations of the sample obtained, anthropology (12.9%), cultural studies (11.8%), teacher education (11.8%) and educational planning (10.6%).

Table 18: Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequenc y	Percentag e										
Linguistics and modern languages	4	22,2%	1	5,6%	2	18,2%	1	25,0%	2	5,9%	10	11,8%
Modern History	3	16,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	5	14,7%	8	9,4%
Classical languages and linguistics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	25,0%	2	5,9%	3	3,5%
Ancient and Medieval History	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	9,1%	1	25,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,4%
Modern Literature	2	11,1%	3	16,7%	1	9,1%	0	0,0%	1	2,9%	7	8,2%
Anthropology	0	0,0%	2	11,1%	2	18,2%	1	25,0%	6	17,6%	11	12,9%
Theory of literature	2	11,1%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,4%
Ethnography and ethnology	0	0,0%	1	5,6%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,2%
Education theory	0	0,0%	3	16,7%	1	9,1%	0	0,0%	4	11,8%	8	9,4%
Cultural studies	1	5,6%	3	16,7%	2	18,2%	0	0,0%	4	11,8%	10	11,8%
Educational planning	2	11,1%	1	5,6%	1	9,1%	0	0,0%	5	14,7%	9	10,6%
Teaching	2	11,1%	3	16,7%	1	9,1%	0	0,0%	4	11,8%	10	11,8%
Contemporary history	2	11,1%	1	5,6%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	2,9%	4	4,7%
Total	18	100,0%	18	100,0%	11	100,0%	4	100,0%	34	100,0%	85	100,0%

The following graph shows the total results already noted in the previous table (last column) for the priority research areas.

Figure 8 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

The preferred research priorities at the University of Jena are threefold: climatology (21.4%), oceanography (14.3%) and circular economy.

Table 19 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)												
	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequenc y	Percentag e										
Atmospheric Sciences	0	0,0%	1	5,6%	0	0,0%	1	25,0%	4	10,5%	6	6,7%
Meteorology	0	0,0%	1	5,6%	0	0,0%	1	25,0%	3	7,9%	5	5,6%
Climatology	4	25,0%	3	16,7%	3	21,4%	2	50,0%	7	18,4%	19	21,1%
Oceanography	2	12,5%	3	16,7%	2	14,3%	0	0,0%	4	10,5%	11	12,2%
Geochemistry	2	12,5%	2	11,1%	2	14,3%	0	0,0%	1	2,6%	7	7,8%
Agronomy	0	0,0%	1	5,6%	2	14,3%	0	0,0%	1	2,6%	4	4,4%
Geodesy	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Physics	2	12,5%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,2%
Geography	0	0,0%	2	11,1%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,2%
Environmental Technology	3	18,8%	3	16,7%	2	14,3%	0	0,0%	5	13,2%	13	14,4%
Geology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Economics of technological change	1	6,3%	1	5,6%	1	7,1%	0	0,0%	5	13,2%	8	8,9%
Geophysics	1	6,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,1%
Circular economy	1	6,3%	1	5,6%	1	7,1%	0	0,0%	6	15,8%	9	10,0%
Hydrology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	7,1%	0	0,0%	2	5,3%	3	3,3%
Total	16	100,0%	18	100,0%	14	100,0%	4	100,0%	38	100,0%	90	100,0%

The following graph (Figure 9) shows the total results (last column of the previous table) and, as can be seen, the fields of research cited are the most preferred.

Figure 9 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

In the field of health and quality of life, the preferred priority research topic is public health (12.2%), followed by psychology (11.1%) and preventive medicine (10%).

Table 20 : Assessment of research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being research (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage										
Psychology	3	12,5%	1	5,3%	2	15,4%	0	0,0%	4	12,9%	10	11,1%
Pharmacodynamics	0	0,0%	1	5,3%	1	7,7%	1	33,3%	2	6,5%	5	5,6%
Human physiology	0	0,0%	2	10,5%	2	15,4%	1	33,3%	2	6,5%	7	7,8%
Clinical sciences	2	8,3%	0	0,0%	2	15,4%	1	33,3%	2	6,5%	7	7,8%
Pharmacology	2	8,3%	3	15,8%	1	7,7%	0	0,0%	2	6,5%	8	8,9%
Immunology	1	4,2%	2	10,5%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	6,5%	5	5,6%
Epidemiology	2	8,3%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	3,2%	4	4,4%
Preventive medicine	3	12,5%	2	10,5%	1	7,7%	0	0,0%	3	9,7%	9	10,0%
Microbiology	1	4,2%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,2%
Forensic sciences	1	4,2%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,1%
Psychiatry	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	7,7%	0	0,0%	1	3,2%	2	2,2%
Molecular biology	1	4,2%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,1%
Occupational medicine	0	0,0%	1	5,3%	1	7,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,2%
Public health	1	4,2%	3	15,8%	1	7,7%	0	0,0%	6	19,4%	11	12,2%
Virology	1	4,2%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	3,2%	3	3,3%
Internal medicine	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	7,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,1%
Surgery	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Neurosciences	2	8,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	3,2%	3	3,3%
Nutritional sciences	1	4,2%	1	5,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	6,5%	4	4,4%
Toxicology	1	4,2%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,1%
Pathology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Human biology	2	8,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	6,5%	4	4,4%
Total	24	100,0%	19	100,0%	13	100,0%	3	100,0%	31	100,0%	90	100,0%

The following table (Table 21) presents the contributions made through an open question collected in each of the questionnaires.

Table 21 : Contributions on the relevant research fields in which the EC2U Alliance could start developing joint projects and Virtual Institutes

Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)

No contributions

Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)

No contributions

Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)

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Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes

No contributions

Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students

No contributions

V. University of Pavia

Similarly to the case of the University of Jena, the sample obtained at the University of Pavia (8 responses in the 5 questionnaires) does not allow for an analysis that has a minimum socio-statistical representation with respect to the study universe (university community of Pavia), which is why, in the following pages, we present the results obtained graphically, indicating only each of the subjects dealt with.

Table 22 and Figure 10 show the distribution of the sample obtained (8 responses) in the five questionnaires.

Figure 10 : Distribution of the sample according to the survey

Tabla 22: Distribution of the sample according to the survey

	Frequency	Percentage
Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)	2	25,0%
Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)	1	12,5%
Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)	2	25,0%
Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes	1	12,5%
Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students	2	25,0%
Total	8	100,0%

Table 23 below shows the priority research topics for the near future, although as there is no socio-statistically representative sample, the results offer a bias that does not allow any conclusions to be drawn.

Table 23 : Assessment of priority research topics for society in the near future (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage										
Logic	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	2	10,5%
Medical Sciences	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	5,3%
Linguistics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Mathematics	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	50,0%	0	0,0%	2	10,5%
Technology	0	0,0%	1	50,0%	1	33,3%	1	50,0%	0	0,0%	3	15,8%
Pedagogy	0	0,0%	1	50,0%	1	33,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	10,5%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Anthropology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	1	5,3%
Political Science	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Physics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Demography	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	5,3%
Psychology	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	2	10,5%
Chemistry	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Economic Sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Biological Sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	33,3%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	2	10,5%
Geography	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Sociology	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	5,3%
Space Sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
History	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Ethics	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	2	10,5%
Agricultural sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Law and legal sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Philosophy	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Total	7	100,0%	2	100,0%	3	100,0%	2	100,0%	5	100,0%	19	100,0%

In Table 24, dedicated to pointing out the fields of research that should be a priority at the University of Pavia, medical science (25%) is indicated as the highest priority, although the lack of responses does not allow us to describe the results.

Table 24 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage										
Logic	1	16,7%	1	50,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	25,0%	3	15,0%
Medical Sciences	1	16,7%	1	50,0%	1	16,7%	1	50,0%	1	25,0%	5	25,0%
Linguistics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	33,3%	1	50,0%	0	0,0%	3	15,0%
Mathematics	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	5,0%
Technology	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	5,0%
Pedagogy	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Anthropology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Political Science	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	25,0%	1	5,0%
Physics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	5,0%
Demography	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Psychology	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	5,0%
Chemistry	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Economic Sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Biological Sciences	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	5,0%
Geography	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Sociology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Space Sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	5,0%
History	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Ethics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	1	25,0%	2	10,0%
Agricultural sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Law and legal sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Philosophy	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Total	6	100,0%	2	100,0%	6	100,0%	2	100,0%	4	100,0%	20	100,0%

Similarly, Table 25 points out other priority research fields such as Modern History or Classical Languages and Linguistics, taking into account the lack of methodological relevance of the sample. These results are shown in Figure 11.

Table 25: Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage										
Linguistics and modern languages	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Modern History	1	14,3%	1	50,0%	0	0,0%	1	50,0%	0	0,0%	3	16,7%
Classical languages and linguistics	0	0,0%	1	50,0%	0	0,0%	1	50,0%	1	25,0%	3	16,7%
Ancient and Medieval History	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	25,0%	2	11,1%
Modern Literature	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	1	33,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	11,1%
Anthropology	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	1	33,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	11,1%
Theory of literature	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Ethnography and ethnology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	25,0%	1	5,6%
Education theory	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Cultural studies	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	1	33,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	11,1%
Educational planning	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	5,6%
Teaching	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Contemporary history	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	25,0%	2	11,1%
Total	7	100,0%	2	100,0%	3	100,0%	2	100,0%	4	100,0%	18	100,0%

Figure 11 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

The following table (Table 26) lists some of the research fields that should be given priority at the University of Pavia, such as climatology and oceanography.

Table 26 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage										
Atmospheric Sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	1	4,8%
Meteorology	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	9,5%
Climatology	2	28,6%	0	0,0%	2	40,0%	1	50,0%	1	20,0%	6	28,6%
Oceanography	2	28,6%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	1	50,0%	1	20,0%	5	23,8%
Geochemistry	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Agronomy	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	1	4,8%
Geodesy	0	0,0%	1	50,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	4,8%
Physics	0	0,0%	1	50,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	4,8%
Geography	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Environmental Technology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	4,8%
Geology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Economics of technological change	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	4,8%
Geophysics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Circular economy	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	2	9,5%
Hydrology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Total	7	100,0%	2	100,0%	5	100,0%	2	100,0%	5	100,0%	21	100,0%

Figure 12 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

Table 27 : Assessment of research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being research (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage										
Psychology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	1	4,8%
Pharmacodynamics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Human physiology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Clinical sciences	2	28,6%	1	50,0%	0	0,0%	1	50,0%	0	0,0%	4	19,0%
Pharmacology	1	14,3%	1	50,0%	1	20,0%	1	50,0%	2	40,0%	6	28,6%
Immunology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	40,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	9,5%
Epidemiology	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	4,8%
Preventive medicine	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	9,5%
Microbiology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Forensic sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Psychiatry	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Molecular biology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	1	4,8%
Occupational medicine	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Public health	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	4,8%
Virology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	4,8%
Internal medicine	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Surgery	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Neurosciences	1	14,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	2	9,5%
Nutritional sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Toxicology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Pathology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Human biology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Total	7	100,0%	2	100,0%	5	100,0%	2	100,0%	5	100,0%	21	100,0%

The research topics to be prioritised in the field of health and quality of life are listed in Table 27 and in the last table (Table 28), the contributions obtained in the open questions.

Table 28 : Contributions on the relevant research fields in which the EC2U Alliance could start developing joint projects and Virtual Institutes

Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)

Etica della ricerca scientifica e misure di impatto sociale della ricerca
Comunicazione della scienza e cittadinanza scientifica

Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)

No contributions

Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)

No contributions

Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes

No contributions

Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students

No contributions

VI. University of Poitiers

The sample obtained at the University of Poitiers is 194 responses, adding up the responses obtained in the five questionnaires. The highest level of response was achieved in Questionnaire 3 (61 responses) and Questionnaire 4 (53 responses) as shown in the following table (Table 29).

Table 29: Distribution of the sample according to the survey

	Frequency	Percentage
Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)	31	16,0%
Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)	16	8,2%
Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)	61	31,4%
Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes	53	27,3%
Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students	33	17,0%
Total	194	100,0%

The sample is distributed, proportionally, in Figure 13, as follows: 31.4% of responses to Questionnaire 3 (Teachers-Researchers), 27.3% of the total belong to Questionnaire 4 (Doctoral Students), Questionnaire 5 represents 17% (Students and Interested Staff), Questionnaire 1 has 16% of responses and Questionnaire 2 (8.2%).

Figure 13 : Distribution of the sample according to the survey

The topics that should be a priority for society in the near future, according to the responses obtained, shown below (Table 30), are, in this order, the following: Medical Sciences (15.4%), Technology (9.1%) and Space Sciences (8.6%).

Table 30 : Assessment of priority research topics for society in the near future (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	1,3%	0	0,0%	2	0,3%
Medical Sciences	16	18,8%	5	10,4%	30	16,5%	20	12,6%	17	17,2%	88	15,4%
Linguistics	1	1,2%	2	4,2%	2	1,1%	0	0,0%	1	1,0%	6	1,0%
Mathematics	3	3,5%	4	8,3%	3	1,6%	8	5,0%	2	2,0%	20	3,5%
Technology	10	11,8%	4	8,3%	14	7,7%	16	10,1%	8	8,1%	52	9,1%
Pedagogy	6	7,1%	1	2,1%	11	6,0%	11	6,9%	9	9,1%	38	6,6%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	1	1,2%	1	2,1%	2	1,1%	2	1,3%	0	0,0%	6	1,0%
Anthropology	1	1,2%	0	0,0%	5	2,7%	1	0,6%	2	2,0%	9	1,6%
Political Science	1	1,2%	2	4,2%	3	1,6%	4	2,5%	2	2,0%	12	2,1%
Physics	4	4,7%	0	0,0%	9	4,9%	14	8,8%	1	1,0%	28	4,9%
Demography	0	0,0%	5	10,4%	5	2,7%	3	1,9%	4	4,0%	17	3,0%
Psychology	2	2,4%	1	2,1%	3	1,6%	9	5,7%	3	3,0%	18	3,1%
Chemistry	3	3,5%	0	0,0%	9	4,9%	12	7,5%	3	3,0%	27	4,7%
Economic Sciences	2	2,4%	5	10,4%	9	4,9%	6	3,8%	1	1,0%	23	4,0%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	3	3,5%	0	0,0%	2	1,1%	1	0,6%	3	3,0%	9	1,6%
Biological Sciences	13	15,3%	5	10,4%	17	9,3%	13	8,2%	7	7,1%	55	9,6%
Geography	0	0,0%	1	2,1%	4	2,2%	3	1,9%	1	1,0%	9	1,6%
Sociology	4	4,7%	0	0,0%	3	1,6%	5	3,1%	1	1,0%	13	2,3%
Space Sciences	5	5,9%	2	4,2%	21	11,5%	8	5,0%	13	13,1%	49	8,6%
History	3	3,5%	1	2,1%	9	4,9%	4	2,5%	1	1,0%	18	3,1%
Ethics	2	2,4%	3	6,3%	6	3,3%	3	1,9%	4	4,0%	18	3,1%
Agricultural sciences	1	1,2%	5	10,4%	7	3,8%	10	6,3%	9	9,1%	32	5,6%
Law and legal sciences	3	3,5%	0	0,0%	7	3,8%	2	1,3%	5	5,1%	17	3,0%
Philosophy	1	1,2%	1	2,1%	1	0,5%	2	1,3%	2	2,0%	7	1,2%
Total	85	100,0%	48	100,0%	182	100,0%	159	100,0%	99	100,0%	573	100,0%

Table 31 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Logic	0	0,0%	1	2,1%	0	0,0%	5	3,4%	0	0,0%	6	1,1%
Medical Sciences	17	20,0%	6	12,5%	23	14,3%	12	8,3%	17	17,3%	75	14,0%
Linguistics	1	1,2%	0	0,0%	2	1,2%	1	0,7%	2	2,0%	6	1,1%
Mathematics	4	4,7%	2	4,2%	7	4,3%	7	4,8%	2	2,0%	22	4,1%
Technology	8	9,4%	5	10,4%	16	9,9%	18	12,4%	7	7,1%	54	10,1%
Pedagogy	7	8,2%	4	8,3%	10	6,2%	10	6,9%	11	11,2%	42	7,8%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	0,6%	2	1,4%	0	0,0%	3	0,6%
Anthropology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	4	2,5%	2	1,4%	1	1,0%	7	1,3%
Political Science	1	1,2%	2	4,2%	4	2,5%	1	0,7%	1	1,0%	9	1,7%
Physics	5	5,9%	2	4,2%	10	6,2%	16	11,0%	3	3,1%	36	6,7%
Demography	0	0,0%	3	6,3%	2	1,2%	1	0,7%	2	2,0%	8	1,5%
Psychology	3	3,5%	2	4,2%	3	1,9%	7	4,8%	4	4,1%	19	3,5%
Chemistry	6	7,1%	1	2,1%	10	6,2%	13	9,0%	2	2,0%	32	6,0%
Economic Sciences	3	3,5%	2	4,2%	7	4,3%	5	3,4%	2	2,0%	19	3,5%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	2	2,4%	1	2,1%	2	1,2%	2	1,4%	4	4,1%	11	2,0%
Biological Sciences	11	12,9%	5	10,4%	17	10,6%	11	7,6%	7	7,1%	51	9,5%
Geography	1	1,2%	1	2,1%	1	0,6%	2	1,4%	1	1,0%	6	1,1%
Sociology	2	2,4%	0	0,0%	1	0,6%	4	2,8%	1	1,0%	8	1,5%
Space Sciences	7	8,2%	3	6,3%	16	9,9%	12	8,3%	10	10,2%	48	8,9%
History	1	1,2%	1	2,1%	6	3,7%	2	1,4%	1	1,0%	11	2,0%
Ethics	1	1,2%	1	2,1%	4	2,5%	1	0,7%	4	4,1%	11	2,0%
Agricultural sciences	1	1,2%	5	10,4%	5	3,1%	7	4,8%	8	8,2%	26	4,8%
Law and legal sciences	2	2,4%	0	0,0%	9	5,6%	3	2,1%	7	7,1%	21	3,9%
Philosophy	2	2,4%	1	2,1%	1	0,6%	1	0,7%	1	1,0%	6	1,1%
Total	85	100,0%	48	100,0%	161	100,0%	145	100,0%	98	100,0%	537	100,0%

At the University of Poitiers, the preferred fields that should be given priority in this first question, based on the answers obtained (above 10% or very close to it), are Medical Sciences (14%), Technology (10.1%) and Biology (9.5%).

In the second of the items, dedicated to the fields of research that should be a priority at the University of Poitiers itself, Teaching and Educational Theory stand out in particular, and at a greater distance, Cultural Studies and Educational Planning.

Table 32: Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Linguistics and modern languages	6	7,4%	4	8,7%	5	3,3%	9	6,1%	7	7,4%	31	6,0%
Modern History	8	9,9%	3	6,5%	13	8,6%	15	10,1%	3	3,2%	42	8,1%
Classical languages and linguistics	2	2,5%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	6	4,1%	0	0,0%	8	1,5%
Ancient and Medieval History	5	6,2%	1	2,2%	13	8,6%	12	8,1%	6	6,4%	37	7,1%
Modern Literature	5	6,2%	3	6,5%	3	2,0%	6	4,1%	3	3,2%	20	3,8%
Anthropology	4	4,9%	1	2,2%	16	10,6%	9	6,1%	8	8,5%	38	7,3%
Theory of literature	0	0,0%	1	2,2%	3	2,0%	2	1,4%	1	1,1%	7	1,3%
Ethnography and ethnology	5	6,2%	1	2,2%	9	6,0%	12	8,1%	5	5,3%	32	6,2%
Education theory	10	12,3%	7	15,2%	21	13,9%	23	15,5%	14	14,9%	75	14,4%
Cultural studies	8	9,9%	6	13,0%	12	7,9%	16	10,8%	7	7,4%	49	9,4%
Educational planning	6	7,4%	7	15,2%	15	9,9%	3	2,0%	14	14,9%	45	8,7%
Teaching	13	16,0%	8	17,4%	24	15,9%	22	14,9%	19	20,2%	86	16,5%
Contemporary history	9	11,1%	4	8,7%	17	11,3%	13	8,8%	7	7,4%	50	9,6%
Total	81	100,0%	46	100,0%	151	100,0%	148	100,0%	94	100,0%	520	100,0%

Thus, we can see graphically (Graph 14) that 16.5% of the responses obtained from the information gathered in the five questionnaires prefer Teaching over Educational Theory (14.4%), while below 10%, as we have already pointed out, indicate Cultural Studies (9.4%) and Educational Planning (8.7%).

Figure 14 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

Table 33 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage										
Atmospheric Sciences	7	9,7%	2	4,3%	7	4,3%	10	6,5%	6	5,9%	32	5,9%
Meteorology	4	5,6%	1	2,1%	2	1,2%	9	5,9%	7	6,9%	23	4,3%
Climatology	1	1,4%	6	12,8%	25	15,2%	27	17,6%	15	14,7%	74	13,8%
Oceanography	9	12,5%	5	10,6%	18	11,0%	15	9,8%	13	12,7%	60	11,2%
Geochemistry	3	4,2%	1	2,1%	5	3,0%	9	5,9%	4	3,9%	22	4,1%
Agronomy	8	11,1%	6	12,8%	18	11,0%	17	11,1%	10	9,8%	59	11,0%
Geodesy	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	4	2,4%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	4	0,7%
Physics	5	6,9%	0	0,0%	6	3,7%	11	7,2%	1	1,0%	23	4,3%
Geography	1	1,4%	2	4,3%	4	2,4%	4	2,6%	0	0,0%	11	2,0%
Environmental Technology	9	12,5%	9	19,1%	20	12,2%	20	13,1%	13	12,7%	71	13,2%
Geology	1	1,4%	0	0,0%	6	3,7%	3	2,0%	2	2,0%	12	2,2%
Economics of technological change	10	13,9%	4	8,5%	11	6,7%	6	3,9%	7	6,9%	38	7,1%
Geophysics	2	2,8%	0	0,0%	2	1,2%	4	2,6%	1	1,0%	9	1,7%
Circular economy	8	11,1%	7	14,9%	16	9,8%	9	5,9%	11	10,8%	51	9,5%
Hydrology	4	5,6%	4	8,5%	20	12,2%	9	5,9%	12	11,8%	49	9,1%
Total	72	100,0%	47	100,0%	164	100,0%	153	100,0%	102	100,0%	538	100,0%

The third of the items dedicated to the research fields that should be a priority, related to the environment and sustainability, stand out for over 10%: Climatology, Environmental Technology, Oceanography; on the other hand, 9.5% are also committed to the circular economy and hydrology (9.1%).

In Figure 15 we can see the results noted above, where Oceanography (13.8%) and Environmental Technology (13.2%) stand out.

Figure 15 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

There is a greater diversity of preferences in the case of the question on priority research topics in the field of health and well-being (see Table 34); although Preventive Medicine is the topic with the highest response rate (10.4%) and, below 10%, Epidemiology (8.5%) and Public Health (8.1%).

Table 34 : Assessment of research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being research (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Psychology	5	5,3%	3	6,4%	11	6,3%	12	7,6%	9	8,7%	40	6,9%
Pharmacodynamics	3	3,2%	1	2,1%	2	1,1%	2	1,3%	1	1,0%	9	1,6%
Human physiology	6	6,3%	2	4,3%	7	4,0%	6	3,8%	2	1,9%	23	4,0%
Clinical sciences	9	9,5%	2	4,3%	11	6,3%	10	6,3%	7	6,8%	39	6,7%
Pharmacology	6	6,3%	3	6,4%	7	4,0%	3	1,9%	4	3,9%	23	4,0%
Immunology	9	9,5%	5	10,6%	10	5,7%	7	4,4%	10	9,7%	41	7,1%
Epidemiology	8	8,4%	3	6,4%	14	8,0%	13	8,2%	11	10,7%	49	8,5%
Preventive medicine	11	11,6%	6	12,8%	17	9,7%	16	10,1%	10	9,7%	60	10,4%
Microbiology	1	1,1%	0	0,0%	9	5,1%	3	1,9%	3	2,9%	16	2,8%
Forensic sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	1,1%	1	0,6%	1	1,0%	4	0,7%
Psychiatry	3	3,2%	1	2,1%	12	6,8%	13	8,2%	5	4,9%	34	5,9%
Molecular biology	3	3,2%	1	2,1%	4	2,3%	4	2,5%	1	1,0%	13	2,2%
Occupational medicine	2	2,1%	3	6,4%	5	2,8%	1	0,6%	6	5,8%	17	2,9%
Public health	5	5,3%	6	12,8%	12	6,8%	17	10,8%	7	6,8%	47	8,1%
Virology	4	4,2%	2	4,3%	11	6,3%	5	3,2%	7	6,8%	29	5,0%
Internal medicine	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	1,1%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	0,3%
Surgery	2	2,1%	2	4,3%	2	1,1%	7	4,4%	4	3,9%	17	2,9%
Neurosciences	8	8,4%	1	2,1%	11	6,3%	15	9,5%	5	4,9%	40	6,9%
Nutritional sciences	1	1,1%	4	8,5%	12	6,8%	13	8,2%	6	5,8%	36	6,2%
Toxicology	2	2,1%	2	4,3%	4	2,3%	3	1,9%	2	1,9%	13	2,2%
Pathology	3	3,2%	0	0,0%	4	2,3%	1	0,6%	1	1,0%	9	1,6%
Human biology	4	4,2%	0	0,0%	7	4,0%	6	3,8%	1	1,0%	18	3,1%
Total	95	100,0%	47	100,0%	176	100,0%	158	100,0%	103	100,0%	579	100,0%

Finally, the contributions made in each of the questionnaires are indicated through the open questions summarised in the following table (Table 35).

Table 35 : Contributions on the relevant research fields in which the EC2U Alliance could start developing joint projects and Virtual Institutes

Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)

ODDs n°16, n°10 et n°7

Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)

Qualité de l'eau

Effondrement de la biodiversité

Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)

l'impact du changement climatique

Glycosciences

Sciences de gestion

Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes

Économie de la décroissance

Permaculture

Habitat écologique

Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students

No contributions

VII. University of Salamanca

The University of Salamanca has obtained a total sample, adding up the five questionnaires, of 663 surveys answered. The highest level of response was found in Questionnaire 3, Teachers-Researchers, with 38.8%, compared to 28.2% in Questionnaire 5 (28.2%), aimed at Students and Stakeholders, followed by Questionnaire 4 (21.6%), Doctoral Students, while Questionnaire 1 (6.6%) and Questionnaire 2 (4.8%) had fewer responses.

Table 36: Distribution of the sample according to the survey

	Frequency	Percentage
Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)	44	6,6%
Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)	32	4,8%
Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)	257	38,8%
Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes	143	21,6%
Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students	187	28,2%
Total	663	100,0%

Figure 16 below shows the distribution of the sample described above.

Figure 16 : Distribution of the sample according to the survey

As in the rest of the universities, the research topics that should have the highest priority for society in the near future (Table 37) are Medical Sciences (16.4%) and Technology (12.3%); the rest of the answers reflect a certain diversity in which there are hardly any differences between a majority of topics.

Table 37 : Assessment of priority research topics for society in the near future (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage								
Logic	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	12	1,4%	10	1,8%	11	1,7%	33	1,4%
Medical Sciences	25	14,9%	22	18,8%	150	17,8%	88	16,0%	95	15,0%	380	16,4%
Linguistics	5	3,0%	5	4,3%	23	2,7%	10	1,8%	27	4,3%	70	3,0%
Mathematics	10	6,0%	7	6,0%	31	3,7%	21	3,8%	22	3,5%	91	3,9%
Technology	18	10,7%	17	14,5%	110	13,0%	60	10,9%	80	12,6%	285	12,3%
Pedagogy	4	2,4%	3	2,6%	27	3,2%	40	7,3%	26	4,1%	100	4,3%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	1	0,6%	1	0,9%	11	1,3%	11	2,0%	13	2,1%	37	1,6%
Anthropology	1	0,6%	0	0,0%	11	1,3%	9	1,6%	7	1,1%	28	1,2%
Political Science	3	1,8%	1	0,9%	16	1,9%	19	3,4%	9	1,4%	48	2,1%
Physics	8	4,8%	7	6,0%	31	3,7%	16	2,9%	23	3,6%	85	3,7%
Demography	4	2,4%	5	4,3%	19	2,2%	7	1,3%	8	1,3%	43	1,9%
Psychology	7	4,2%	10	8,5%	48	5,7%	36	6,5%	53	8,4%	154	6,7%
Chemistry	3	1,8%	4	3,4%	25	3,0%	13	2,4%	16	2,5%	61	2,6%
Economic Sciences	8	4,8%	4	3,4%	33	3,9%	21	3,8%	35	5,5%	101	4,4%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	12	7,1%	3	2,6%	64	7,6%	37	6,7%	46	7,3%	162	7,0%
Biological Sciences	15	8,9%	6	5,1%	55	6,5%	22	4,0%	24	3,8%	122	5,3%
Geography	2	1,2%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	0,4%	6	0,9%	10	0,4%
Sociology	7	4,2%	1	0,9%	16	1,9%	15	2,7%	11	1,7%	50	2,2%
Space Sciences	2	1,2%	3	2,6%	28	3,3%	15	2,7%	27	4,3%	75	3,2%
History	9	5,4%	1	0,9%	15	1,8%	8	1,5%	11	1,7%	44	1,9%
Ethics	3	1,8%	4	3,4%	30	3,6%	33	6,0%	27	4,3%	97	4,2%
Agricultural sciences	11	6,5%	12	10,3%	39	4,6%	18	3,3%	15	2,4%	95	4,1%
Law and legal sciences	4	2,4%	0	0,0%	21	2,5%	21	3,8%	25	3,9%	71	3,1%
Philosophy	6	3,6%	1	0,9%	30	3,6%	19	3,4%	16	2,5%	72	3,1%
Total	168	100,0%	117	100,0%	845	100,0%	551	100,0%	633	100,0%	2314	100,0%

In the first of the items (Table 38) related to the research fields that should be a priority at their University (University of Salamanca), the answers obtained in the previous case are repeated, as both Medical Sciences (15.4%) and Technology (10.7%) are the preferred fields.

Table 38 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage								
Logic	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	11	1,4%	10	2,0%	10	1,7%	31	1,5%
Medical Sciences	22	13,7%	19	17,4%	132	17,0%	70	14,1%	84	14,6%	327	15,4%
Linguistics	12	7,5%	4	3,7%	46	5,9%	21	4,2%	45	7,8%	128	6,0%
Mathematics	7	4,3%	11	10,1%	22	2,8%	22	4,4%	26	4,5%	88	4,2%
Technology	15	9,3%	13	11,9%	85	11,0%	47	9,5%	67	11,6%	227	10,7%
Pedagogy	4	2,5%	3	2,8%	22	2,8%	32	6,5%	14	2,4%	75	3,5%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	6	0,8%	7	1,4%	10	1,7%	23	1,1%
Anthropology	2	1,2%	0	0,0%	7	0,9%	9	1,8%	7	1,2%	25	1,2%
Political Science	3	1,9%	2	1,8%	15	1,9%	14	2,8%	12	2,1%	46	2,2%
Physics	9	5,6%	8	7,3%	32	4,1%	11	2,2%	19	3,3%	79	3,7%
Demography	2	1,2%	4	3,7%	10	1,3%	4	0,8%	4	0,7%	24	1,1%
Psychology	4	2,5%	8	7,3%	36	4,6%	32	6,5%	40	6,9%	120	5,7%
Chemistry	7	4,3%	3	2,8%	22	2,8%	10	2,0%	12	2,1%	54	2,6%
Economic Sciences	5	3,1%	4	3,7%	22	2,8%	17	3,4%	28	4,9%	76	3,6%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	17	10,6%	7	6,4%	76	9,8%	44	8,9%	49	8,5%	193	9,1%
Biological Sciences	10	6,2%	4	3,7%	55	7,1%	21	4,2%	23	4,0%	113	5,3%
Geography	1	0,6%	0	0,0%	3	0,4%	3	0,6%	6	1,0%	13	0,6%
Sociology	5	3,1%	0	0,0%	14	1,8%	9	1,8%	11	1,9%	39	1,8%
Space Sciences	3	1,9%	2	1,8%	25	3,2%	18	3,6%	22	3,8%	70	3,3%
History	7	4,3%	2	1,8%	23	3,0%	13	2,6%	13	2,3%	58	2,7%
Ethics	4	2,5%	2	1,8%	17	2,2%	23	4,6%	16	2,8%	62	2,9%
Agricultural sciences	12	7,5%	12	11,0%	34	4,4%	17	3,4%	16	2,8%	91	4,3%
Law and legal sciences	5	3,1%	1	0,9%	37	4,8%	22	4,4%	28	4,9%	93	4,4%
Philosophy	5	3,1%	0	0,0%	23	3,0%	20	4,0%	14	2,4%	62	2,9%
Total	161	100,0%	109	100,0%	775	100,0%	496	100,0%	576	100,0%	2117	100,0%

Table 39 shows the preferences of the University of Salamanca (second item) regarding the fields of research that should be a priority at this University. The preferences reflect three fields, mainly Linguistics and Modern Languages (13.8%), the one with the highest preference, followed by Cultural Studies (11.5%) and Educational Planning (11.3%).

Table 39: Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Linguistics and modern languages	23	15,8%	16	16,2%	95	13,3%	54	11,3%	88	15,7%	276	13,8%
Modern History	10	6,8%	4	4,0%	55	7,7%	33	6,9%	39	7,0%	141	7,1%
Classical languages and linguistics	11	7,5%	4	4,0%	42	5,9%	18	3,8%	41	7,3%	116	5,8%
Ancient and Medieval History	7	4,8%	2	2,0%	38	5,3%	14	2,9%	30	5,3%	91	4,6%
Modern Literature	2	1,4%	8	8,1%	44	6,2%	22	4,6%	21	3,7%	97	4,9%
Anthropology	12	8,2%	6	6,1%	51	7,2%	36	7,6%	46	8,2%	151	7,6%
Theory of literature	6	4,1%	2	2,0%	26	3,6%	14	2,9%	15	2,7%	63	3,2%
Ethnography and ethnology	10	6,8%	3	3,0%	30	4,2%	21	4,4%	21	3,7%	85	4,3%
Education theory	11	7,5%	10	10,1%	61	8,6%	69	14,5%	47	8,4%	198	9,9%
Cultural studies	19	13,0%	8	8,1%	75	10,5%	66	13,9%	62	11,1%	230	11,5%
Educational planning	15	10,3%	17	17,2%	81	11,4%	55	11,6%	58	10,3%	226	11,3%
Teaching	5	3,4%	12	12,1%	53	7,4%	38	8,0%	45	8,0%	153	7,7%
Contemporary history	15	10,3%	7	7,1%	62	8,7%	36	7,6%	48	8,6%	168	8,4%
Total	146	100,0%	99	100,0%	713	100,0%	476	100,0%	561	100,0%	1995	100,0%

In addition to the preferred fields of research, the following graph (Graph 17) shows the overall results, where other fields obtain a lower preference (below 10%), such as Educational Theory (9.9%) or Contemporary History (8.4%).

Figure 17 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

The third item concerning the research fields that should be a priority at the University of Salamanca revealed four of them, in line with the responses obtained in the other universities, with Environmental Technology being the most frequently mentioned field (14.6%), Climatology (13.1%), Agronomy (10.6%) and Economy of technological change (10%).

Table 40 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage								
Atmospheric Sciences	8	5,5%	6	5,4%	60	7,8%	34	7,0%	51	8,7%	159	7,6%
Meteorology	6	4,1%	3	2,7%	31	4,0%	19	3,9%	23	3,9%	82	3,9%
Climatology	26	17,9%	10	9,0%	100	12,9%	64	13,2%	74	12,7%	274	13,1%
Oceanography	8	5,5%	6	5,4%	54	7,0%	30	6,2%	55	9,4%	153	7,3%
Geochemistry	5	3,4%	2	1,8%	15	1,9%	12	2,5%	12	2,1%	46	2,2%
Agronomy	15	10,3%	16	14,4%	84	10,9%	48	9,9%	59	10,1%	222	10,6%
Geodesy	1	0,7%	2	1,8%	9	1,2%	4	0,8%	6	1,0%	22	1,0%
Physics	10	6,9%	3	2,7%	36	4,7%	28	5,8%	20	3,4%	97	4,6%
Geography	3	2,1%	3	2,7%	17	2,2%	17	3,5%	12	2,1%	52	2,5%
Environmental Technology	20	13,8%	21	18,9%	108	14,0%	73	15,1%	84	14,4%	306	14,6%
Geology	2	1,4%	0	0,0%	15	1,9%	13	2,7%	17	2,9%	47	2,2%
Economics of technological change	13	9,0%	9	8,1%	78	10,1%	48	9,9%	61	10,4%	209	10,0%
Geophysics	1	0,7%	1	0,9%	14	1,8%	11	2,3%	12	2,1%	39	1,9%
Circular economy	14	9,7%	15	13,5%	78	10,1%	42	8,7%	54	9,2%	203	9,7%
Hydrology	13	9,0%	14	12,6%	74	9,6%	42	8,7%	44	7,5%	187	8,9%
Total	145	100,0%	111	100,0%	773	100,0%	485	100,0%	584	100,0%	2098	100,0%

These same results are expressed, graphically, below and after the fields of research mentioned above, others appear (Figure 18) (below 10%) such as the circular economy (9.7%) or Hydrology (8.9%), which are also significant for the sustainable transformation of the socio-economic development model.

Figure 18 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

As in the rest of the universities, the research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being were evaluated (Table 41), obtaining next results; Psychology (11.4%) or Preventive Medicine (10.6%) and, below 10%, others such as Neuroscience (8.8%).

Table 41 : Assessment of research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being research (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage								
Psychology	14	7,9%	11	9,3%	85	9,9%	72	12,9%	82	13,5%	264	11,4%
Pharmacodynamics	2	1,1%	2	1,7%	14	1,6%	12	2,1%	8	1,3%	38	1,6%
Human physiology	4	2,2%	0	0,0%	13	1,5%	17	3,0%	12	2,0%	46	2,0%
Clinical sciences	6	3,4%	2	1,7%	32	3,7%	18	3,2%	16	2,6%	74	3,2%
Pharmacology	9	5,1%	5	4,2%	56	6,5%	32	5,7%	40	6,6%	142	6,1%
Immunology	13	7,3%	11	9,3%	73	8,5%	40	7,2%	52	8,6%	189	8,2%
Epidemiology	11	6,2%	12	10,2%	66	7,7%	39	7,0%	52	8,6%	180	7,8%
Preventive medicine	16	9,0%	17	14,4%	89	10,4%	65	11,6%	58	9,6%	245	10,6%
Microbiology	7	3,9%	2	1,7%	31	3,6%	15	2,7%	22	3,6%	77	3,3%
Forensic sciences	1	0,6%	0	0,0%	2	0,2%	5	0,9%	2	0,3%	10	0,4%
Psychiatry	10	5,6%	7	5,9%	28	3,3%	35	6,3%	50	8,2%	130	5,6%
Molecular biology	16	9,0%	7	5,9%	41	4,8%	25	4,5%	22	3,6%	111	4,8%
Occupational medicine	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	7	0,8%	3	0,5%	4	0,7%	14	0,6%
Public health	12	6,7%	18	15,3%	84	9,8%	55	9,8%	27	4,4%	196	8,5%
Virology	7	3,9%	4	3,4%	36	4,2%	14	2,5%	21	3,5%	82	3,5%
Internal medicine	6	3,4%	2	1,7%	24	2,8%	9	1,6%	7	1,2%	48	2,1%
Surgery	5	2,8%	1	0,8%	18	2,1%	9	1,6%	24	4,0%	57	2,5%
Neurosciences	21	11,8%	9	7,6%	91	10,6%	42	7,5%	42	6,9%	205	8,8%
Nutritional sciences	8	4,5%	7	5,9%	34	4,0%	22	3,9%	33	5,4%	104	4,5%
Toxicology	1	0,6%	1	0,8%	8	0,9%	6	1,1%	8	1,3%	24	1,0%
Pathology	4	2,2%	0	0,0%	11	1,3%	6	1,1%	7	1,2%	28	1,2%
Human biology	5	2,8%	0	0,0%	14	1,6%	18	3,2%	18	3,0%	55	2,4%
Total	178	100,0%	118	100,0%	857	100,0%	559	100,0%	607	100,0%	2319	100,0%

The contributions made by the different agents related to the university community of the University of Salamanca who have responded to each of the questionnaires are now reported. The contributions have been collected by means of an open question.

Table 42 : Contributions on the relevant research fields in which the EC2U Alliance could start developing joint projects and Virtual Institutes

Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)

Humanidades
Ciencias médicas
Ciencias sociales y jurídicas
Economía circular
Ingeniería y tecnología
Identidad cultural y religiosa

Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)

Sostenibilidad en relación con los Alimentos.
Recuperación y Reciclaje de Materiales.
Aprovechamiento y Reutilización de todo tipo de productos.
Importancia de las Zoonosis.
Educación
Sostenibilidad

Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)

Ciencias políticas
Humanidades y Ciencias Sociales
Física, energía y Fotónica
Ecología lingüística y cultural
Patrimonio
Vulnerabilidad Social
Riesgos laborales
Políticas públicas y gobernanza
Medicina preventiva

Sostenibilidad y consumo
Educación
Pobreza y colectivos excluidos
Consumo energético
Desequilibrios y marginación en zonas rurales
Estudios de género
Lenguas modernas
Economía circular y cambio climático
Ejercicio físico y salud
Multilinguismo

Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes

Identidades
Inteligencia Artificial
Derechos humanos
Prevaricación y corrupción
Influencia de la religión en las decisiones políticas
Pérdida auditiva
Educación Rural
Evaluación como práctica pedagógica
Medicina preventiva
Psicología
Educación
Agoralimentación
Ciencias del Deporte

Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students

Investigación médica
Cambio climático
Educación

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035803

Enseñanza de idiomas
Medicina preventiva
Desarrollo sostenible
Historia de la literatura
Psicoanálisis
Sostenibilidad
energías renovables
Lengua y literatura clásica
Biodiversidad

VIII. University of Turku

The responses obtained at the University of Turku are 67 (Table 43), adding the five questionnaires together, so that the socio-statistical representativeness is not the most adequate. When describing and evaluating the tables below, the lack of socio-statistical relevance should be taken into account.

Table 43: Distribution of the sample according to the survey

	Frequency	Percentage
Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)	3	4,5%
Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)	3	4,5%
Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)	28	41,8%
Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes	16	23,9%
Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students	17	25,4%
Total	67	100,0%

In the following graph (Graph 19) we can see the responses obtained in each of the five Questionnaires until the sample is complete (67 responses), of which 41.8% belong to Questionnaire 3 (teachers-researchers), and to a lesser extent, to Questionnaire 5 (25.4%), addressed to Students and Questionnaire 4 (23.9%), Doctoral Students. Questionnaire 1 and 2 have 3 responses each.

Figure 19 : Distribution of the sample according to the survey

Table 44 : Assessment of priority research topics for society in the near future (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage								
Logic	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,4%	2	3,7%	0	0,0%	3	1,7%
Medical Sciences	1	16,7%	1	20,0%	11	14,9%	5	9,3%	6	17,1%	24	13,8%
Linguistics	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	5	6,8%	0	0,0%	1	2,9%	7	4,0%
Mathematics	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	1	1,4%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	1,1%
Technology	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	6	8,1%	4	7,4%	4	11,4%	15	8,6%
Pedagogy	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,4%	2	3,7%	1	2,9%	4	2,3%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,4%	0	0,0%	1	2,9%	2	1,1%
Anthropology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	3	4,1%	1	1,9%	0	0,0%	4	2,3%
Political Science	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	1	1,4%	1	1,9%	3	8,6%	6	3,4%
Physics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,4%	1	1,9%	1	2,9%	3	1,7%
Demography	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	2	2,7%	1	1,9%	0	0,0%	4	2,3%
Psychology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,7%	4	7,4%	1	2,9%	7	4,0%
Chemistry	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,4%	1	1,9%	0	0,0%	2	1,1%
Economic Sciences	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	0	0,0%	4	7,4%	1	2,9%	6	3,4%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	3	4,1%	0	0,0%	1	2,9%	4	2,3%
Biological Sciences	0	0,0%	1	20,0%	7	9,5%	8	14,8%	2	5,7%	18	10,3%
Geography	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,4%	0	0,0%	1	2,9%	2	1,1%
Sociology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	4	5,4%	3	5,6%	1	2,9%	8	4,6%
Space Sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	7	9,5%	5	9,3%	6	17,1%	18	10,3%
History	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	3	4,1%	2	3,7%	0	0,0%	6	3,4%
Ethics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	6	8,1%	4	7,4%	1	2,9%	11	6,3%
Agricultural sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	4	5,4%	4	7,4%	3	8,6%	11	6,3%
Law and legal sciences	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	2	2,7%	2	3,7%	0	0,0%	5	2,9%
Philosophy	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,4%	0	0,0%	1	2,9%	2	1,1%
Total	6	100,0%	5	100,0%	74	100,0%	54	100,0%	35	100,0%	174	100,0%

Table 45 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage								
Logic	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	3,2%	3	6,0%	0	0,0%	5	3,3%
Medical Sciences	1	12,5%	0	0,0%	10	16,1%	5	10,0%	6	20,0%	22	14,4%
Linguistics	1	12,5%	0	0,0%	6	9,7%	0	0,0%	1	3,3%	8	5,2%
Mathematics	1	12,5%	0	0,0%	1	1,6%	0	0,0%	1	3,3%	3	2,0%
Technology	0	0,0%	1	33,3%	9	14,5%	6	12,0%	5	16,7%	21	13,7%
Pedagogy	1	12,5%	0	0,0%	3	4,8%	3	6,0%	1	3,3%	8	5,2%
Astronomy and Astrophysics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Anthropology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	2,0%	0	0,0%	1	0,7%
Political Science	1	12,5%	0	0,0%	1	1,6%	2	4,0%	0	0,0%	4	2,6%
Physics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,6%	1	2,0%	1	3,3%	3	2,0%
Demography	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	2,0%	0	0,0%	1	0,7%
Psychology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	3	4,8%	4	8,0%	1	3,3%	8	5,2%
Chemistry	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	2,0%	0	0,0%	1	0,7%
Economic Sciences	0	0,0%	1	33,3%	1	1,6%	2	4,0%	2	6,7%	6	3,9%
Humanities, Arts and Literature	2	25,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,6%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	3	2,0%
Biological Sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	8	12,9%	6	12,0%	3	10,0%	17	11,1%
Geography	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	3,3%	1	0,7%
Sociology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	3,2%	3	6,0%	2	6,7%	7	4,6%
Space Sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	3,2%	4	8,0%	4	13,3%	10	6,5%
History	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	3,2%	3	6,0%	0	0,0%	5	3,3%
Ethics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	5	8,1%	3	6,0%	0	0,0%	8	5,2%
Agricultural sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	3,2%	1	2,0%	1	3,3%	4	2,6%
Law and legal sciences	0	0,0%	1	33,3%	2	3,2%	0	0,0%	1	3,3%	4	2,6%
Philosophy	1	12,5%	0	0,0%	1	1,6%	1	2,0%	0	0,0%	3	2,0%
Total	8	100,0%	3	100,0%	62	100,0%	50	100,0%	30	100,0%	153	100,0%

Table 46: Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage								
Linguistics and modern languages	1	11,1%	0	0,0%	8	11,8%	2	4,5%	3	10,7%	14	9,3%
Modern History	1	11,1%	0	0,0%	4	5,9%	4	9,1%	2	7,1%	11	7,3%
Classical languages and linguistics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,9%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	1,3%
Ancient and Medieval History	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	6	8,8%	0	0,0%	1	3,6%	7	4,6%
Modern Literature	1	11,1%	0	0,0%	3	4,4%	3	6,8%	0	0,0%	7	4,6%
Anthropology	2	22,2%	0	0,0%	4	5,9%	4	9,1%	2	7,1%	12	7,9%
Theory of literature	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	3	4,4%	1	2,3%	0	0,0%	4	2,6%
Ethnography and ethnology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	4	5,9%	3	6,8%	2	7,1%	9	6,0%
Education theory	1	11,1%	0	0,0%	8	11,8%	6	13,6%	2	7,1%	17	11,3%
Cultural studies	2	22,2%	0	0,0%	9	13,2%	8	18,2%	4	14,3%	23	15,2%
Educational planning	0	0,0%	1	50,0%	3	4,4%	5	11,4%	5	17,9%	14	9,3%
Teaching	0	0,0%	1	50,0%	10	14,7%	5	11,4%	5	17,9%	21	13,9%
Contemporary history	1	11,1%	0	0,0%	4	5,9%	3	6,8%	2	7,1%	10	6,6%
Total	9	100,0%	2	100,0%	68	100,0%	44	100,0%	28	100,0%	151	100,0%

In the first of the items (Table 45) concerning the research fields that should be a priority at their university, Medical Science (14.4%), Technology (13.7%) and Biological Sciences (11.1%) are preferred.

Table 46 shows the responses to the second item concerning the priority research fields at their university; Cultural Studies (15.2%), Teaching (13.9%) and Educational Theory (11.3%) are the most significant.

In the following graph we can see these results (Figure 20) where, logically, other less representative fields of research also appear, such as Educational Planning (9.3%) or Linguistics and Modern Languages (9.3%).

Figure 20 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

In the third of the items relating to the research topics that should be a priority, taking into account the lack of socio-statistical representativeness of the sample obtained, different preferences are projected (Table 47).

Table 47 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage										
Atmospheric Sciences	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	7	10,9%	4	8,0%	4	11,1%	16	10,1%
Meteorology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	3,1%	1	2,0%	0	0,0%	3	1,9%
Climatology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	12	18,8%	6	12,0%	7	19,4%	25	15,7%
Oceanography	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	5	7,8%	4	8,0%	4	11,1%	14	8,8%
Geochemistry	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,6%	2	4,0%	0	0,0%	3	1,9%
Agronomy	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	3	4,7%	5	10,0%	4	11,1%	12	7,5%
Geodesy	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Physics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	3,1%	0	0,0%	1	2,8%	3	1,9%
Geography	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,6%	4	8,0%	1	2,8%	6	3,8%
Environmental Technology	1	16,7%	1	33,3%	12	18,8%	11	22,0%	5	13,9%	30	18,9%
Geology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	2,8%	1	0,6%
Economics of technological change	1	16,7%	1	33,3%	6	9,4%	5	10,0%	5	13,9%	18	11,3%
Geophysics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Circular economy	1	16,7%	1	33,3%	10	15,6%	8	16,0%	2	5,6%	22	13,8%
Hydrology	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	3	4,7%	0	0,0%	2	5,6%	6	3,8%
Total	6	100,0%	3	100,0%	64	100,0%	50	100,0%	36	100,0%	159	100,0%

Figure 21 : Rating of the research fields that should be given priority at your university (Multi-choice: maximum five options) Total Results

These preferences are shown graphically in Graph 21: Environmental Technology (18.9%), Climatology (15.7%), Digital Economy (11.3%) and Atmospheric Science (10.1%).

In terms of priority research topics in the field of health and well-being, Public Health (11.4%), Immunology (10.2%) and Psychology (10.2%).

Table 48 : Assessment of research topics that should be a priority in the field of health and well-being research (Multi-choice: maximum five options)

	S1		S2		S3		S4		S5		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage								
Psychology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	6	8,6%	8	15,4%	3	8,6%	17	10,2%
Pharmacodynamics	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,4%	0	0,0%	2	5,7%	3	1,8%
Human physiology	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	3	4,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	4	2,4%
Clinical sciences	0	0,0%	1	25,0%	5	7,1%	2	3,8%	5	14,3%	13	7,8%
Pharmacology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	4	5,7%	1	1,9%	1	2,9%	6	3,6%
Immunology	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	6	8,6%	4	7,7%	6	17,1%	17	10,2%
Epidemiology	0	0,0%	1	25,0%	6	8,6%	3	5,8%	2	5,7%	12	7,2%
Preventive medicine	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	7	10,0%	4	7,7%	2	5,7%	14	8,4%
Microbiology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,9%	2	3,8%	0	0,0%	4	2,4%
Forensic sciences	1	16,7%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	0,6%
Psychiatry	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,9%	4	7,7%	2	5,7%	8	4,8%
Molecular biology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	4	5,7%	1	1,9%	1	2,9%	6	3,6%
Occupational medicine	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	3,8%	0	0,0%	2	1,2%
Public health	1	16,7%	1	25,0%	6	8,6%	7	13,5%	4	11,4%	19	11,4%
Virology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	5	7,1%	0	0,0%	3	8,6%	8	4,8%
Internal medicine	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,4%	2	3,8%	0	0,0%	3	1,8%
Surgery	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Neurosciences	1	16,7%	1	25,0%	4	5,7%	4	7,7%	1	2,9%	11	6,6%
Nutritional sciences	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	3	4,3%	4	7,7%	1	2,9%	8	4,8%
Toxicology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	3	4,3%	2	3,8%	2	5,7%	7	4,2%
Pathology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	1,9%	0	0,0%	1	0,6%
Human biology	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	2	2,9%	1	1,9%	0	0,0%	3	1,8%
Total	6	100,0%	4	100,0%	70	100,0%	52	100,0%	35	100,0%	167	100,0%

Finally, the contributions collected in each of the questionnaires are presented.

Table 49 : Contributions on the relevant research fields in which the EC2U Alliance could start developing joint projects and Virtual Institutes

Survey 1: Political survey on research (University managers)

No contributions

Survey 2: Political survey on research (Political and socioeconomic stakeholders)

No contributions

Survey 3: Survey on individual research necessities and attitudes (Researches/Teachers)

Translation in different areas of life and occupations
Molecular Ecology

Survey 4: Survey on individual PhD research necessities and attitudes

Informatics and data analysis
Biology, physics, chemistry, sociology
Sustainability, agriculture, food, and energy are being spotlighted

Survey 5: Survey on perceived R&I needs for interested social groups and students

Sustainability and climate change

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